

A review on multi-material 3D-printing of functional materials via vat photopolymerization

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Abstract: Additive manufacturing or 3D-printing of materials is a prominent process technology, which involves the fabrication of materials layer-by-layer or point-by-point in a subsequent manner. With the recent advancements in additive manufacturing, the technology has excited a great potential for extension of simple designs to complex multi-material geometries. Vat photopolymerization is a sub-division of additive manufacturing, which possesses many attractive features such as excellent printing resolution, high dimensional accuracy, low cost manufacturing and ability to spatially control the material properties. However, the technology is certainly limited by design strategies, material chemistries and equipment limitations. This review is aimed to provide the readers with a comprehensive comparison of additive manufacturing technologies and detailed knowledge on advances in multi-material vat-photopolymerization technologies. Furthermore, we describe the popular material chemistries from the past and recent era along with the future prospects to cop-up with the material related limitations undergone within vat photopolymerization. The impressive multi-material capabilities inspired by nature are applicable today in multiple areas of life, which have been briefly presented in the applications section. Finally, we demonstrate our point of view on the future prospects of 3D printed multi-material structures and the way forward to promising further advancements in vat-photopolymerization.

Keywords: 3D-printing; vat photopolymerization; multimaterials; step-growth; chain-growth; cationic polymerization; orthogonal networks; grayscale printing.

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1. Introduction

Polymers have revolutionized the world with their diversity, tempting appearances, inherent properties and unique functionality. They are macromolecules formed by repeating monomer units and thus, they exhibit exceptional physical, mechanical and viscoelastic properties. Because of their long chemically bonded macromolecular chains, mechanical and thermal stimuli can induce mobility and deformations in polymers [1].

The vast variety of monomers and the adjoining mechanisms give rise to polymers differing in flexibility, stiffness and elasticity. Based on their crosslink structure and related thermo-mechanical and viscoelastic properties, they are divided into thermoplastics, elastomers and thermosets, which collectively represent a huge share among the technically relevant materials available at the market [2]. As the name suggests, thermoplastics are high molecular weight polymers, which do not possess chemical crosslinks and thus, at elevated temperature they become mobile, soft and flowable enough to be shaped into commodity articles [3]. Cooling the shaped articles below the glass and melting temperature hardens the thermoplastic objects and fixes the thermoplastic's microstructure. Thermoplastics can be processed by injection molding, extrusion and upon heating, they can be softened, melted and reshaped repeatedly. In contrast, duromers, thermosets or thermosetting polymers are highly crosslinked polymer networks, which get hard and

cure into a permanent shape during processing [4]. Such curing reactions are typically induced by heat or ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) light irradiation and form irreversible crosslinks within the polymer structure [2]. Owing to the highly cross-linked nature and the inherent rigidity of the polymer network, recycling of diuremers is challenging as they are not soluble and infusible. Elastomers also contain chemical crosslinks, albeit at a lower degree than diuremers. They are soft rubberlike polymers with very low glass transition temperature and notably lower Young's modulus. They are typically known for their exceptional stretchability beyond their original dimensions [5]. Elastomers are interchangeably denoted as rubbers, due to the inherent elasticity and amorphous nature, which induces considerable segmental mobility within the chemical bonds [6].

The mechanical properties, especially the stiffness of the final polymer product is greatly affected by its composition, macromolecular structure and number/type of crosslinks. The stiffness of a polymer is a measure of the ratio of the applied force to the strain produced in the material. Technically expressed as the Young's modulus (E), it is defined by the tangent of the modulus in the linear elastic region, and typically determined at an initial strain $< 2\%$ [7].

The Young's modulus of polymers represents an important property that discriminates between soft and stiff materials. Table 1 compares the Young's moduli of selected polymers with other material classes. Elastomers and hydrogels are soft with a Young's modulus in the range of $10^3 - 10^9$ Pa, which is comparable to the rigidity of natural soft tissues such as muscles or skin. Thus, these classes of materials dominate sectors such as biomedical engineering [8–10], soft robotics [11–15] and flexible electronics [16–18].

In contrast, structural thermoplastic polymers have a Young's modulus between $10^9 - 10^{12}$ Pa, which is in the range of the Young's modulus of wood or bone [1,11].

Table 1. Young's moduli of selected soft and rigid materials [1,11,19]

Category	Material	Young's Modulus (Pa)
Soft	Brain tissues	10^3
	Alginate hydrogel Fat	10^4
	Silicone elastomer	10^5
	Polydimethylsiloxane	0.8×10^6
	Polycaprolactone	0.2×10^7
	Biological skin	0.5×10^8
	Rubber	0.8×10^8
	Polyethylene (Low density)	0.5×10^9
	Polylactic acid	0.5×10^{10}
	Nylon	0.6×10^{10}
Rigid	Wood	10^{10}
	Polymethylmethacrylate	4.5×10^{10}
	Polyethylene terephthalate	5.5×10^{10}
	Bone	0.5×10^{11}
	Glass	0.8×10^{11}
	Copper	10^{11}
	Steel	0.5×10^{12}
Diamond	10^{12}	

Until now, various processing strategies have been adopted for the manufacturing of multi-material structures, which contain soft as well as rigid domains. This particular interest in multimaterial manufacturing is inspired by nature, where countless exemplary multi-material architectures of soft and hard constituents, including nacre [20], shells [21], wood [22], bones [23,24] or exoskeleton crustaceans [25], exhibit unique features in terms of mechanical properties and functionality.

In particular for the formation of 3D objects with multi-material properties, additive manufacturing or 3D-printing of polymers offers significant advantages over conventional processing methodologies. The single-step manufacturing of complex 3-dimensional products, along with drastically shortened processing times have gained increased attention over the past decade [21,26–41].

The designed structures are evolved layer-by-layer or point-by-point via computerized controlled system to replicate the desired 3D shape models. Contrary to traditional processing methods, which require the use of dies, molds or lithography masks, 3D-printing technologies employ automated assemblies that translate the computer-aided-designs into sophisticated 3D-structures without excess material losses.

Furthermore, the ability to quickly develop the final products with lower process complexity along with the lower costs of printing technologies has attracted both academia and industry. To date, more than fifty different types of additive manufacturing technologies have been reported on the basis of the processing principles [1]. The choice of the technology being used for the manufacturing of a specific product greatly depends on the physical and chemical properties of the raw materials and the targeted end applications of the final product.

As thermoplastics become repeatedly soft and processable above the melting temperature they are processable by extrusion based additive manufacturing technologies. However, due to their limited mechanical properties, they are not always suitable for structural applications in neat condition and it is often essential to add particular additives such as reinforcing fillers to adjust the properties of the 3D printed articles [42,43]. However, due to the absence of covalent bonds, 3D printed thermoplastics can be easily reprocessed and re-melted.

In contrast, 3D printed thermosets and duromers cannot be reprocessed, as chemical crosslinks are formed during the printing process. These curing reactions are generally irreversible and once covalently crosslinked, the materials are insoluble and infusible. Curing reactions are typically triggered by temperature or light. In particular, optically triggered curing reactions comprise several advantages such as fast curing under mild conditions (even at room temperature), spatial control of the reaction and low energy consumption [44–46]. These make photoreactions ideal candidates for additive manufacturing. In vat photopolymerization 3D-printing, a liquid photocurable resins is selectively cured by light exposure and the structure is formed layer-by-layer (digital light processing 3D-printing) or point-by-point (stereolithography). These vat photopolymerization additive manufacturing technologies employ a variety of different functional monomers including epoxy resins, phenolic polymers, unsaturated polyesters, acrylates and methacrylates or organosilicons [47]. Additive manufacturing of such systems could generate soft materials but also photopolymers with higher mechanical strength and stiffness similar to that of dental resins [48].

Among the established additive manufacturing technologies, vat photopolymerization technologies outperform in terms of excellent building resolution, dimensional accuracy, diversified reaction chemistries, low equipment costs and high surface quality [41,49,50]. Due to the attractive features of vat photopolymerization, recent advancements have extended the materials fabrication capacity and numerous types of techniques have been established including stereolithography (SLA), digital light processing (DLP), liquid crystal display (LCD) printing, continuous liquid interface printing (CLIP) and two photon absorption (TPA) printing. In this review paper, we will primarily focus on vat photopolymerization based 3D-printing technologies and discuss in detail the manufacturing processes, the accessible feedstock chemicals and underlying curing mechanisms. Furthermore, we will exclusively target the advancements on multi-material vat photopolymerization and its ability to spatially control mechanical properties by a combination of multiple materials and reaction chemistries within 3D printed architectures. In a systematic way, we will develop the understanding of the whole multi-material vat photopolymerization domain and present some recent advances.

Growing number of experts and researchers with diverse backgrounds have started utilizing additive manufacturing technology for developing complex objects with multi-material properties, which could not be produced using traditional processing techniques. Many remarkable and overreaching results have been reported in the last couple of years [51,52], which offer significant potential to revolutionize the next generation of functional materials. Furthermore, the number of publications in the last decade has also increased significantly (Figure 1), representing a great perception of the research field. At the moment, extrusion based technologies (fused filament fabrication, direct ink writing) are mostly employed for additive manufacturing of polymers, but they suffer from a lower spatial resolution and poor multi-material building capabilities at the molecular scale (e.g. poor adhesion at the interface between soft and rigid domains) [41]. Here, vat photopolymerization technologies could offer the required spatial and temporal control with the nanoscale interactions of the reacting precursors.

Nonetheless, multi-material vat photopolymerization 3D-printing persists in the early development phases and encounters various challenges: (1) limited functionality of monomers, (2) limited library of photopolymers supporting multi-material printing technology, (3) loss of reactions' orthogonality, (4) leaching of the material and long-term property maintenance, (5) viscosity and printability of precursors with a suitable resolution.

Figure 1. The number of research articles published on multi-material additive manufacturing since 2010 (source: Scopus).

To highlight the full capabilities of multi-material vat photopolymerization 3D-printing, the multi-material printing process itself and the vat photopolymerization strategies will be addressed in this review. At the end, we will emphasize the application-oriented aspects of multi-material vat photopolymerization 3D-printing in flexible electronics, biomedical applications, soft robotics and rapid-prototyping. In addition, we will discuss new concepts to increase the sustainability and recyclability of the highly crosslinked 3D structures, which rely on the introduction of dynamic covalent bonds.

2. Additive manufacturing technologies

Additive manufacturing technology or 3D-printing of polymers can be generally classified into extrusion-based technologies (fused filament extrusion, direct ink writing), polymer bed sintering, vat photopolymerization based technologies (stereolithography, digital light processing, liquid crystal display printing, continuous liquid interface printing, two photon absorption printing) and 3D-volumetric polymerization technologies.

Each technology has its own advantages and limitations, and the choice of the processing methodology depends on the feed materials, required printing resolution, printing times, size and performance of printed materials and overall cost of fabrication [53–56].

In this section, we briefly illustrate the processing techniques and highlight their key features and executive summary in Table 3 at the end.

2.1. Material extrusion (fused filament fabrication)

Fused filament fabrication (FFF) is the most widely used 3D-printing technology for thermoplastic polymers. In this process, polymeric filaments are fed into the extrusion head, where they are melted into a semi-liquid state. Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polylactic acid (PLA) and polycarbonate (PC) are the most widely used thermoplastic filaments due to their low processing temperatures. The molten polymers are then extruded through the nozzle on the building platform, where the melt is allowed to cool down and fuse together (Figure 2). The motion of the extrusion nozzle is controlled layer-by-layer according to the 3D-design interpretation.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the fused filament fabrication (FFF) process [7,57].

Adjustment of printing parameters such as temperature, building orientation, air gap, raster angle and width and thickness of layers plays a vital role in the quality of 3D-printed articles [7,57]. A major constrain with utilizing FFF technology is the limitation to feed polymers in filament form. The requirement of high temperatures, acceptable viscosity range for extrusion, homogenous and void-free melt flow represent some of the challenging areas in FFF. On the other hand, lower cost of printing, simplicity of the process and the fast building speed makes FFF a very attractive technology for additive manufacturing of 3D objects.

2.2. Direct ink writing

Direct ink writing (DIW) involves the extrusion of viscoelastic liquid pastes through a pressurized nozzle. The material is extruded on a fixed platform and allowed to cool down and solidifies, while the nozzle can move and defines the shape of the printed material (Figure 3). The final structure of the material is fixed via layer-by-layer deposition of the liquid polymer ink [39,58]. The viscosity of the extruded liquid and the speed of the extrusion defines the quality of the printed architectures [59]. The primary benefit of this technology is the material versatility as polymer solutions, hydrogels and pastes can be easily charged into the extrusion nozzle. A sacrificial structural support may be required for the fabrication of complex architectures as the viscoelastic nature of the material could collapse the 3D object during building.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the direct ink writing (DIW) process [7].

2.3. Selective laser sintering

In the selective laser sintering (SLS) 3D-printing technique, a solid polymer powder bed is locally heated with a scanning laser. Laser illumination causes the melting and fusion of the polymeric powder, which is spread over the surface of the build platform by a rolling assembly. The spatially controlled exposure to laser light causes the melting of the polymer at selective regions. For the next layer, a piston assembly moves one step down to accumulate the polymer powder with the help of a spreading roller (Figure 4). The whole process is repeated until the required number of layers is achieved according to the printing program [60]. With powerful, high energy laser scans, the adjacent polymer particles could also fuse and molecularly diffuse into the printed structure. The removal of unbounded materials during a post-processing step is essential to achieve good resolution of printed articles.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the selective laser sintering laser (SLS) process [60].

Particle size of polymeric powder, scanning speed, scan width and gap, and laser intensity have an impact on the final structure of the printed materials [61]. In SLS technology, ideally any thermoplastic powder could be fused and processed, but the molecular diffusion, complicated integration and sintering of particles, greatly limit the number of processable polymers [62]. Widely used polymers in SLS include polyamide and polycaprolactone.

2.4. Stereolithography

Stereolithography (SLA) is a vat photopolymerization process, in which liquid resins with adequate viscosity are introduced into a vat. Light is illuminated on the liquid resin in a controlled manner, resulting in the polymerization reaction at the targeted positions (Figure 5). The 3D structure is evolved by illumination of the 3D design point-by-point guided by the 3D interpretation software [27,63,64]. Liquid resins such as methacrylates, acrylates, vinyl and epoxy monomers are typically used in SLA technology. The quality of the printed structures depends on the cure kinetics of polymerization process, which is guided by the light intensity, illumination time, resin viscosity, chemical functionality, and the additives in the formulations. Photoinitiators and light absorbers are introduced in the formulations to initiate the reactions and to improve the resolution of the printed object, respectively.

Figure 5. Schematic diagram of the stereolithography (SLA) process.

The key benefit of SLA technology is the very high resolution of the printed objects. Furthermore, as the monomers are already in liquid form, any sort of heating of the polymer feed and nozzle is not required. Unfortunately, the technology is limited by the number of available photopolymers. Cytotoxicity and irritation potential of the resins and the unreacted monomers in the printed articles should be considered while 3D-printing using SLA [65].

2.5 Digital light processing

Digital light processing (DLP) is another class of vat photopolymerization technology, in which illumination with light starts the polymerization reaction locally. Liquid resins containing vinyl, acrylate or epoxide groups are often employed along with a suitable photoinitiator and light absorber. In contrast to SLA, the liquid resin is irradiated layer-by-layer according to the design of the printing article (Figure 6). Photoinitiators absorb the light in a certain wavelength range according to their absorption capability and trigger the polymerization reaction in the illuminated regions. Polymerization takes place and the final printed article is formed by solidification of each layer. After printing, the object is removed from the build platform, while the remaining resin is recovered from the vat [66,67].

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of the digital light processing (DLP) process.

The key benefit of DLP 3D-printing is the high resolution of the final product and fast building speed. Like SLA, DLP technology is also limited by the availability of monomers that can be photopolymerized.

2.6 Liquid crystal display

Liquid crystal display (LCD) is another a vat photopolymerization technology, which uses a liquid crystal display unit for the imaging tasks. By applying an electric field, molecular rearrangements of the liquid crystals take place, which block the passage of light through selective areas (Figure 7). The design of the 3D-printed structure is translated through the computerized system, which creates the response in the LCD imaging unit. With the leading LCD technology, very high printing resolution can be achieved. Despite of the promising LCD technology, some molecular rearrangements can remain trapped or stuck under the application of an electric field, which enables the passage of light through the LCD screen resulting in reduced resolution [68–70].

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of the liquid crystal display (LCD) printing process.

2.7 Continuous liquid interface printing

Continuous liquid interface printing (CLIP) technology was introduced in 2015, and permits a continuous printing of monolithic and layer-less photopolymeric architectures [71]. The technology is based on the utilization of an oxygen permeable chamber allowing the formation of an interfacial oxygen layer. The radical induced polymerization reaction is inhibited by the presence of the oxygen layer. This oxygen interference could quench the excited phase of photoinitiators and can also form peroxides by reacting with free radicals in the polymerizing system [72]. As a result, unreacted monomers remain at the interface between build platform and oxygen layer. This results in rapid printing of polymer resins without slicing the 3D-designs and avoiding the conventional layer-by-layer approach (Figure 8). CLIP technology typically can draw-out printed objects at a very fast

speed with production cycles of only a few minutes and a resolution lower than $100\ \mu\text{m}$ [71,73,74]. However, it is limited to curing systems, which are quenched by oxygen such as photocurable (meth)acrylate-based monomers.

Figure 8. Schematic diagram of the continuous liquid interface printing (CLIP) process [75].

2.8 Hot-lithography

Hot lithography process employs the principles of vat photopolymerization technology with the difference that the vat is additionally supplied by a heating element, which is able to control the temperature of the printing process. During conventional vat photopolymerization processes, the printing temperature is kept at room temperature, which is sometimes limited by the higher viscosity of the printing resins. By taking advantage of higher temperature processing, hot-lithography could not only reduce the viscosity of the resins but also increases the reactivity of monomers, which could not be fully polymerized at room temperature [76–78]. Photocurable resins are cured by applying a typical SLA or DLP projector, but the conversion of monomers could be expected to be higher in comparison to room temperature curing [77]. This technology offers the potential to enhance the resin portfolio, which could be vat photopolymerized.

Figure 9. Schematic diagram of the hot-lithography process.

2.9 Two photon absorption 3D-printing

Two photon absorption 3D-printing (TPA or TPP) is a vat photopolymerization technique, which employs a highly compact laser beam as light source. The extremely high-power density of illumination in the range of $10^{13}\ \text{W}/\mu\text{m}^2$, on a very confined volume of less than a cubic wavelength λ^3 , results in photon absorption in a nonlinear pattern (i.e. two photon absorption) [79]. Hence an excellent spatial resolution (i.e. nanometer range), far ahead of the optical diffraction limit is realized [80]. To take complete advantage of non-linear absorption, an infrared irradiation source is adopted, to facilitate the deep penetration of laser light into the bulk of matter, minimizing absorption power losses. In case of lithography where the light is linearly exposed, the material response only corresponds

to the first order. However, the response is also of the second or multiple orders as a result of two photon or multi photon absorption respectively (Figure 10). The square light intensity distribution is spatially more precise than the linear one [80], consequently decreasing the light-matter interaction volume and results in improved printing resolution. The photoinitiator absorbs two photons in the near-infrared range (NIR), providing a similar quantum of energy that is supplied by the single photon absorption in a photocurable formulation. Hence, spatially distributed photoinitiated radicals formed during two photon polymerization of resins also follow the square law of light intensity function. Due to the presence of radical scavengers such as dissolved oxygen in the resin formulations, radicals are sustained in the regions of higher light intensity, and a polymerization threshold is attained. This light intensity corresponding to the threshold is also adjustable using printing parameters such illumination time, target unit volume (i.e. voxels), and illumination intensity. Using TPA, printing resolutions much lower than the defined diffraction limit could be achieved [81–86]. With adjustments in 3D-printing parameters, voxels up to 100 nm were 3D-printed [80,87,88].

Figure 10. UV light is absorbed at the surface of a photosensitive resin and can only be used for fabrication of planar structures (one photon absorption). NIR light is focused into the volume of the photocurable resin and is used for 3D structuring (TPP). Reproduced with permission from [89]. Copyright © 2006 Elsevier.

TPA 3D-printing can be used to fabricate nanostructures that could not be developed with other technologies. Owing to a very strong transient power, laser illumination in TPA can activate multiple reactive species in the resins, hence a suitable strategy is required to effectively use the process for the 3D-printing of nanostructures.

Table 2. Some printing strategies and application of TPA polymerizations

	Processing strategy	Application area	Resolution achieved	Reference
TPA Photo polymerization	Radical quencher	Microstructures	100 nm	[90]
	Activation beam	Microdevices	40 nm	[91]
	Scanning speed manipulation	Micromachines	25 nm	[92]
	Self-smoothing	Micro-optics	20 nm	[93]

2.10 Volumetric 3D-printing

Volumetric 3D-printing is a process in which multiple sliced images are DLP projected at distinct angles on a synchronized rotating resin chamber according to the computer-aided-designs [94,95]. While the intensity of a single illuminated ray is deficient enough to avoid the photopolymerization of resin under oxygen inhibition, the

superposition of exposed irradiation leads to the activation of radical species above a threshold, resulting in the polymerization of a centimeter scale object in a matter of few seconds. The degree of polymerization for each resin can be adjusted by tuning the light intensity and the exposure duration. For such volumetric techniques, resins with a higher viscosity (up to 90 Pa.s) can be 3D-printed [94]. Typically, flexible polymers with an elastic modulus of <10 kPa and discrete applications such as bio-imprints and tissue engineering could be challenging to print using layer-by-layer printing technologies. Here, gravitational and auxiliary forces occur during printing, which result in a frequent breakage of the layers and building structure. Volumetric 3D-printing can easily overcome these problems by avoiding the layer-by-layer approach. Using volumetric printing technologies, a resolution of 80 μm has been achieved [96] with a printing speed much higher than conventional vat photopolymerization based technologies. There are many classes of volumetric 3D-printing techniques including computer axial lithography (CAL), xolography [49], tomographic printing [95,96] and holographic light patterning [97]. While the technology is still under development stages, a few of them such as xolography printer and tomographic printer (Readily 3D) are also already commercially available, but they have not been extended to multi-material 3D-printing yet.

In contrast, solution mask liquid lithography (SMaLL) is a volumetric 3D-printing technology, which showed the potential to fabricate 3D objects with multi-material properties. In this technology, collimated UV and Vis light is illuminated over an optically dense resin consisting of a combination of photocurable monomers, photoinitiators, photochromes and photosensitizers. Particular interest is generated here by the photochromes, which are added to deploy photo-bleaching fronts capable of activating the photosensitizers and subsequently deep curing the materials, which significantly enhances the building speed. During the 3D-printing, the reversible absorption characteristics of the photochromic dyes are exploited to locally activate or deactivate photoreactions at different wavelengths [21].

Table 3. Characteristics of selected commonly used 3D-printing technologies

	Suitable materials	Resolution	Building speed	Benefits	Limitations	Reference
Fused filament fabrication (FFF)	Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene, nylon, polylactic acid, polyethylene terephthalate, polyvinylalcohol, high impact polystyrene, thermoplastic polyurethane, polycarbonate, polypropylene	100 μm	1-10 m/min	Ability to print large functional materials with standard thermoplastic polymers	Low resolution, nozzle chocking, filament non-homogeneous melting, material anisotropy along z-axis	[1,32,38,42,98,99]
Direct ink writing (DIW)	Liquid polymer/melt/gel/paste	1 - 100 μm	3 m/min	Highest resolution among all extrusion processes	Higher cost, not suitable for complex geometries	[1,32,38,100–102]
Selective laser sintering (SLS)	Polylaurylamide, polyether ketone, ketone,	80 - 100 μm	1.80-3.6 m/min	Ability to process standard plastics,	Lower resolution, rough surface	[1,7,38,103–106]

		polyamide, polycaprolactone			good mechanical properties	Limited availability of photopolymers, toxicity of monomers	[1,38,64, 104,107– 111]
Stereolithography (SLA)	Acrylate, methacrylate, epoxy, monomers	vinyl	5 - 50 μm	0.25 mm/min	High resolution and accuracy	Limited availability of photopolymers, toxicity of monomers	[1,38,64, 104,107– 111]
Digital light processing (DLP)	Acrylate, methacrylate, epoxy, monomers	vinyl	5 - 50 μm	0.4-2.5 mm/min	High resolution and accuracy, lower cost and higher printing speed compared to SLA	Limited availability of photopolymers, toxicity of monomers	[1,38,110]
Liquid crystalline display (LCD)	Acrylate, methacrylate, epoxy, monomers	vinyl	< 50 μm	10 mm/min	High resolution and accuracy, lower cost	Limited availability of photopolymers, toxicity of monomers	[68– 70,112]
Continuous liquid interface printing (CLIP)	Acrylate, methacrylate, vinyl monomers, epoxies		<100 μm	8-16 mm/min	High printing speed	Anisotropy of printed structures	[113,114]
Two photon absorption (TPA)	Acrylate, methacrylate, vinyl monomers, epoxies		<100 nm	0.08-33 mm ³ /min	Excellent resolution	Expensive, time consuming, requires tedious control strategies (rastering) High viscosity resin (>10 Pa.s)	[115,116]
Volumetric 3D-printing	Acrylate, methacrylate, vinyl monomers, epoxies		Up to 80 μm	10 mm/min	Fast printing speed.	High viscosity resin (>10 Pa.s) required. Costly technology, tedious	[49,94,96 ,117]

Solution mask lithography (SMaLL)	Acrylate, methacrylate, vinyl monomers, epoxies	Up to 100 μm	8.33 mm/min	Large curing depth, no moving parts required, rapid curing rates	resin-formulation strategies, low absorption and high reactivity of monomers required. Additional photochromes and sensitizer required. Reaction strategies to be developed before printing.	[21]
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3. Multi-material 3D-printing

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Multi-material 3D-printing involves the combination of two or more material properties in a single 3D-printed article. The combination of multiple materials can be accomplished through different printing technologies. Among the class of extrusion-based 3D-printing, fused filament fabrication (FFF) is the most widely used 3D-printing technology. The first dual component FFF was perceived in 2002, using modeling of optimization strategy in the FF technology [118]. Afterwards, numerous studies have been reported on the development and fabrication of multi-material structures with FFF [30,37,119,120]. A schematic illustration of a multi-material FFF printer is shown in Figure 11. Multiple nozzles are installed under the extrusion head for melting and ejecting each polymer filament on the build platform. After a desired number of layers is printed, the extrusion process is interrupted and the extrusion head is swapped for the ejection of a second type of filament on the building platform. The process continues until the designed multi-material architecture is evolved.

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Commercial two-elements FFF are available below 10,000 Euros and theoretically offer a resolution up to 100 μm . But the practically achieved figures with commercially available polymers are twice or even higher in number as compared to the theoretical offered features and quite often not reproducible with similar printing settings. Furthermore, additional compounding, melting, mixing or kneading cycles are required during the application of functional materials with magnetic or dielectric properties [34,121–123]. The round nature of the filaments, layer by layer deposition, and the poor adhesion between adjacent layers is a particular limitation in single [123] as well as multi-material FFF technology [124]. Furthermore, the limited range of materials and the thermal processing requirements corresponding to each filament creates challenges in multi-material FFF 3D-printing.

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Figure 11. Schematic diagram of the multi-material FFF process. Central motorized controller adjusts the position of extrusion heads intermittently for layer by layer extrusion of each material.

In contrast to FFF, vat photopolymerization based 3D-printing involves the in-situ polymerization of monomers through photo-reactions. Light is illuminated according to the design of the materials, which causes localized initiation and gelation of the liquid resins. Vat photopolymerization based technologies offer the best solution among all 3D-printing technologies, in view of the outstanding surface finish and printing resolution, lower equipment and energy costs. Moreover, they are well suited for the printing of structures with multi-material properties [50,112,125,126]. The main disadvantage of vat photopolymerization based technologies is the limited number of material classes that are available for photopolymerization. With multi-material printing, the potential is great for the combination of numerous chemical moieties into a single built material that could offer properties entirely different from the individual characteristics of each single component. But to realize multi-material vat photopolymerization 3D-printing, it is essential to understand the photochemistry of the polymerization process.

4. Chemistry of multi-material 3D-printing via vat photopolymerization

The chemistry of the vat photopolymerization technology relies on the light triggered solidification of liquid monomers. Light curable resins are placed in a vat, in which the polymerization reactions take place upon UV/Vis-light exposure in selective and confined areas. Monomers start to react rapidly in the presence of an appropriate photoinitiator and form crosslinked networks in a discrete manner (Figure 12). For the formation of networks with adequate properties and to achieve the required properties, it is vital to understand the structure, functionality and underlying mechanism of the reacting monomers and photoinitiators. Utilizing the curing reaction, photoinitiators are locally activated and solidification of liquid resin takes place layer-by-layer or point-by-point.

Figure 12. Schematic representation of a photo-curable resin prior to and after light exposure highlighting the formation of an insoluble and infusible polymer network.

These reactions typically involve radical induced chain growth polymerization of (meth)acrylates, radical induced step-growth reaction of thiol-ene and thiol-yne systems,

mixed-mode thiol-acrylate polymerization, cationic polymerization of epoxides or vinyl ethers and hybrid reaction mechanisms constituting dual curing networks (Figure 13). However, the rapid radical generation, followed by initiation and propagation steps in radical induced chain growth reactions make them the most often applied candidates among the available polymerization routes [108].

Figure 13. Reaction strategies for vat photopolymerization 3D-printing.

4.1. Light triggered reaction in polymers

Exploiting light to generate and crosslink polymers and to adjust their structural and functional properties has become a versatile synthesis strategy in polymer science. Owing to their numerous advantages such as low energy consumption, spatial control and high yields, photoreactions have become indispensable for numerous industries including microelectronics, medicine, adhesives, coating industry or inks. In particular, energetically unfavorable reactions which normally would need high temperatures to overcome the activation barrier, can be started at room temperature or under mild conditions simply by light exposure [46,127]. For this, irradiation of the full electromagnetic spectrum can be exploited for photoinitiation, whilst the choice of the correct light source is crucial to meet the required energy for the targeted photoreaction. Whilst the energy of irradiation rises with decreasing wavelength, the penetration depth of light decreases at the same time, which often limits the use of photoreactions in thicker samples.[128] **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**

In addition, photo-reactions can be temporally controlled and are conveniently started by switching on the light source on, whilst most processes (e.g. radical polymerization, photoisomerization and photocyclization) can be easily stopped again by turning off the light.[46]

Besides the temporal control, light as an external trigger further enables a spatial control of the reactions in polymers. Control in two dimensions is accomplished by masking or patterning of the incident light. Moreover, light can be focused with optical fibers within a volume facilitating a three-dimensional control of the photoreactions. Numerous polymer processing techniques such as photolithography or vat photopolymerization rely on the spatiotemporal control of phototriggered reactions [46,127].

Photoreactions in polymers typically follow two laws: (i) the Grotthuss-Draper law, which states that only the light absorbed by a molecule is able initiate a photoreaction and

(ii) the Stark-Einstein law, which describes that each absorbed quantum of radiation initiates the reaction of one molecule [129].

Thus, photoreactions only proceed in electronically excited molecules. If the incident light has an adequate energy (spectral emission of the light source has to be overlapping with the absorption spectrum of the molecule), an absorbed photon is able to promote an electron from the illuminated molecule from the HOMO (highest occupied molecular orbital) to the LUMO (lowest un-occupied molecular orbital). The energy of an absorbed photon is described by the Plank law (Equation 1), in which the absorbed energy (E) directly depends on the frequency of the photon (ν) and the Plank's constant (h). The frequency is further a function of the speed of light in vacuum (c) and the wavelength (λ).

$$E = h\nu = hc\lambda \quad (1)$$

By exposure with appropriate wavelength, the electrons of the molecule are promoted from the ground state (S_0) to an excited singlet state (S_n). The excited electron has then varying ways towards deactivation, which are explained in the Jablonski diagram. Following radiationless processes (internal conversion and vibration relaxation), the molecule reaches the lowest excited singlet state (S_1). From S_1 the molecule goes back to the ground state (S_0) by vibration-relaxation, fluorescence or a photochemical reaction (10^{-12} – 10^{-6}). Another possible transition with longer lifetimes (10^{-7} – 10 s) is from the triplet state (T_1), which is reached by intersystem crossing (ISC). This is quantum-mechanically forbidden as the electron's spin has to be inverted. By undergoing vibration-relaxation, phosphorescence or a chemical reaction, the molecule goes from T_1 back to S_0 [129–132].

The absorption of a single illuminated molecule is described by the Beer-Lambert law (Equation 2), in which A is the absorbance of irradiation within a film, ϵ the molar extinction coefficient and c the concentration of the absorbing species. In addition, d corresponds to the optical path length, I_0 to the incident intensity of light and I to the light intensity, which is able to pass through the film. [133]

$$A = \epsilon cd = -\log\left(\frac{I}{I_0}\right) \quad (2)$$

However, not each absorbed photon triggered the desired molecular process. Thus, the quantum yield (φ) has been introduced (Equation 3), which describes the number of times a specific event (N_e) occurs per photon absorbed by the system (N_p).

$$\varphi = \frac{N_e}{N_p} \quad (3)$$

As molar absorption and quantum yield are strongly governed by the wavelength, a high absorption throughout the film is required for ensuring a fast reaction rate. It should be noted that photoreactions are limited the areas of the film where light can be absorbed or intermediates can diffuse. Thus, highly absorptive, pigmented, opaque, filled and/or thick films suffer from light intensity/rate gradients and as a consequence, gradients in material properties.

4.2. Photoinitiators

Photoinitiators are molecules that are capable of generating reactive species in the form of free radicals, anions or cations when they are exposed to ultraviolet (UV), visible (Vis) or near infrared (NIR) light. Photoinitiators are the most essential starting units required for the majority of photopolymerization reactions. Commercial photoinitiators are available in solid or liquid form, and they have to be dissolved in the resin formulations prior to irradiation.

For radical photoinitiators, there are typically two different types of initiation mechanism distinguished: Type I photoinitiators (α -cleavage), which undergo unimolecular

bond cleavage to form radicals, and type II ones, which follow a bimolecular reaction yielding radicals by interaction between the excited states of the absorbing molecule and the second one.

When it comes to a radical photoinitiator, which forms two identical radicals, the rate of initiation R_i (Equation 4) is directly related to the light intensity I_0 , the molar absorptivity (ϵ), the radical efficiency (f), quantum yield (φ) and the concentration of the initiator ($[I]$).

$$R_i = 2f\varphi I_0 [I] \epsilon \quad (4)$$

However, it should be noted that the equation is only valid if the film has a low light attenuation through its cross-section [46].

Type I photoinitiators are typical aromatic carbonyl compounds, including benzoin and its derivatives, benzyl ketals, acetophenones, aminoalkyl phenones, O-acyl- α -oxyimino ketones, α -hydroxyalkyl ketones and acylphosphine oxides, which generate free radicals by α -cleavage upon light exposure (Figure 13) [134–136]. Owing to their high quantum efficiency and reactivity, benzoin derivatives are the most commonly applied photoinitiators. However, they suffer from a short shelf life at room temperature, as the benzylic hydrogen can be easily abstracted [137]. In contrast, acylphosphine oxides benefit from an adequate thermal stability and high reactivity of the generated phosphonyl radicals [138].

Type I photoinitiators (Figure 14) are widely employed for starting crosslink reactions in vat photopolymerization 3D-printing, which mostly uses light sources emitting in the UV/Vis region. Photoinitiators with a high molar extinction coefficient and UV absorption range ($\lambda < 400$ nm) are mostly employed in SLA 3D-printing [139].

Figure 14. Type I photoinitiation mechanism [137].

The intensity and wavelength of the light required to start photocleavage reactions depends on the chemical structure of the photoinitiators. In case of Irgacure 1173 and Irgacure 651 (Table 4), the energy absorption takes place at relatively lower bands and the π to π^* transition occurs in the UV range, which makes them suitable for use in SLA [134].

Figure 15. Type II photoinitiation mechanism [137].

In case of photoinitiators based on phosphine oxide, lower energy level of π^* is exhibited, hence shifting the π to π^* peak towards higher wavelengths, resulting in wide applications in DLP system [134].

In contrast to type I photoinitiators, the initiation rate and curing rate of type II ones is lower, as they follow a bimolecular reaction mechanism. They require the addition of a co-initiator, which facilitate electron transfer or hydrogen abstraction reaction in the presence of the electronically excited initiator molecular (Figure 15) [137]. In particular, light exposure of aromatic ketones, such as benzophenone, thioxanthenes, benzyl and quinones in the presence of hydrogen donors yields ketyl radicals and another radical obtained from the hydrogen donor. [140] For starting the polymerization/crosslinking

reaction, the hydrogen donor radical is usually used. Ketyl radicals are quite stable and do not react with vinyl monomers due to steric hindrance and delocalization of unpaired electrons. However, ketyl radicals are able to terminate the polymerization reaction by forming ketyl species within the growing polymer chains. [141] Onium salts or bromo compounds are often added to the compounds to quench the ketyl radical by oxidation or bromination and thus, to prevent chain termination [137]. It should be noted that the choice of co-initiator (H-donor) is critical for a fast photoinitiation process. Tertiary amines have a reactivity than alcohols or ethers. Most of the photoinitiators are absorbing in the UV-range but by adding appropriate sensitizer the absorption window can be shifted in the visible light spectral region. But there are also bimolecular initiator types, which are directly activated by visible light exposure. One example is camphorquinone in combination with an amine synergist. [142]

The successful application of a photoinitiator depends on the suitable match between its absorption characteristics and the emitting wavelengths of the illuminating light source [55]. A list of commonly used radical photoinitiators used in vat photopolymerization 3D-printing is provided in Table 4.

Table 4. List of radical photoinitiators used in vat photopolymerization 3D-printing

Photoinitiators	Absorption wavelength	Structure	Reference
Phenyl bis (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (BAPO)	295 nm, 370 nm		[143–147]
2-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1-phenyl-propan-1-one (Irgacure 1173)	245 nm, 280 nm, 331 nm		[148]
Ethyl (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (Irgacure TPO-L)	275 nm, 379 nm		[149,150]
2,2-dimethoxy-1-phenylacetophenone (Irgacure 651)	252 nm, 340 nm		[146,151,152]
Diphenyl (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (Irgacure TPO)	295 nm, 368 nm, 380 nm, 393 nm		[153–155]
Bis (4-methoxybenzoyl) diethylgermanium (Ivocerin)	408 nm		[156,157]
Benzophenone	253 nm		[158]
Camphorquinone	468 nm		[143,159,160]

5-amino-2-benzyl-1H-benzo isoquinoline-1,3(2H)-dione (NDP2)	417 nm		[143]
3-hydroxyflavone (3HF)	370-470 nm		[161]

Besides radical photoinitiators, cationic photoinitiators have also gained considerable attention, as they are able to initiate polymerization reactions of epoxy and vinyl ether monomers. In the late 1970s Crivello described the use of onium salts for photochemically initiating cationic polymerizations [20,35].

The initiation relies on the formation of a Brønsted acid (H^+), which is formed by the light triggered decomposition of the onium salt and subsequent reaction with solvents or monomers of the formulation. [37] The chemical structure of the counter-anion governs the acidic strength of the formed acid, which increases with the size and nucleophilicity of the counter-anion [37,38].

Diaryliodonium or triarylsulfonium salts are well known photo-acid generators [162], on account of their remarkable ability to release acids when light is irradiated. Selected derivatives are presented in Figure 16. Upon UV exposure, iodonium salts undergo homolytic and heterolytic cleavage reactions. In case of heterolytic cleavage reaction, an aryl cation is generated while in case of homolytic cleavage, an aryl radical pair or a radical cation is formed [163]. These reactive species react with neighboring monomers or solvent molecules and form strong Brønsted acids (e.g. HF), which are able to initiate cationic polymerization reactions [164].

Diaryliodonium or triarylsulfonium salts typically suffer from a limited absorption (absorption maximum between 200 – 300 nm). One way to shift the initiation to higher wavelengths is the so called radical-induced cationic polymerization. [39] Here the photoacid generator is combined with a Type I or II initiator, which forms free radicals upon visible light irradiation. Once formed, the free radicals are oxidized in the presence of the arylidonium salt and radical cations are generated, which are able to initiate cationic reactions. Other approaches to shift the absorption window to longer wavelengths are the use of dyes as sensitizer [40].

Figure 16. Structure of selected cationic photoinitiators. Reproduced with permission from [162]. Copyright ©2006 John Wiley and Sons.

4.3. Light triggered curing reactions exploited in vat photopolymerization 3D-printing

4.3.1. Chain-growth polymerization reaction

Chain-growth polymerization is a reaction resulting in high molecular weight polymers at early stages of the polymerization process and polymer's yield increases gradually with time [165]. These reactions need to be initiated either by radical or ionic initiators. The formed radicals or ionic species subsequently react with the monomers and the chains start growing, which is termed as initiation reaction. Propagation reactions represent the next step of polymerization progress during which, unsaturated monomers add one by one to the active centers on the growing chain [166]. The final termination of the polymerization reactions could either take place through the combination of active centers, or disproportionation reactions, in which molecular rearrangements take place, exchanging the H-atom and forming a saturated and an unsaturated chain end [167].

Since chain-growth polymerization reactions take place rapidly, material properties vary drastically. Originally low viscous liquids are converted into glassy and highly cross-linked networks in a few seconds, which substantially impacts the polymerization performance and results in a diffusion-controlled regime, heterogenous crosslink density [168–172], delays in achieving equilibrium properties and gradients in concentration and temperature.

For initiation of the polymerization reactions, aforementioned initiators need to be utilized. Under light irradiation, the initiator cleaves into primary radicals, which react with the unsaturated carbon-carbon bonds in the formulation [167,172]. Hence, densely pigmented or dyed films cause gradients in the light intensity and initiation rate [173]. Overall the reaction mass transfer becomes difficult and the initiator's efficiency declines, as primary radicals are increasingly caged and tend to combine [170,174].

The propagation step in chain-growth reactions involves the addition of monomer/oligomer radicals to the unsaturated carbon-carbon bonds, which form further radicals at the chain ends [170,175,176]. The crosslink density increases over the reaction time and leads to the diffusion limitations and vitrification of the polymer. The general propagation reaction rate R_p could be represented as (Equation 5) [167],

$$R_p = k_p[M][M_{n\cdot}] \quad (5)$$

Where k_p represents the propagation rate constant, while $[M]$ and $[M_{n\cdot}]$ represent the concentration of double bonds and total radicals, respectively. Termination of reactions could take place with the combination of two radical species. The ideal termination kinetics does not consider the chain length dependency, radicals trapping and heterogeneity within the evolving network and could be presented as (Equation 6) [167],

$$R_T = 2k_T[M_{n\cdot}]^2 \quad (6)$$

with k_T representing the termination rate constant and $[M_{n\cdot}]$ the overall radical concentration. The termination step is frequently limited by the diffusion-controlled regime, leading to the gel effect or Trommsdorff effect [177]. As mass transfer is limited by diffusion, termination due to the chain combination reactions also becomes challenging, and the concentration of primary radicals increases abruptly, resulting in increased polymerization rates and reaction temperature. This increasing temperature also causes faster radical formation and it becomes difficult to disperse them homogeneously due to the increasing viscosity of the system [178–180]. This could also result in trapping of radical species within the crosslinked networks, and hence they could remain in the polymer over a long service period [165,172,178,179].

4.3.1.1. Radical polymerization

Free radical polymerization is a chain addition reaction in which a radical center starts and propagates the polymerization reaction. These reactions can proceed at room temperature without any extreme conditions. The reaction involves the formation of

radical species by excitation and photocleavage of the photoinitiator, which starts the addition reaction [50]. These free radicals are highly reactive species and attack the monomer molecules, transmitting the active center to the attacked molecule. Hence, the reaction propagates (Figure 17) with the addition of active radical centers to other monomers (having unsaturated carbon bonds) by electron transfer, throughout the activated volume and continuously increases the viscosity of resins leading to the gelation [167,172].

The reaction is terminated by immobilization of the active centers either via combination of radical species or the deprotonation (H-transfer) of active monomers, to form stable macromolecules [167]. Radical induced chain-growth polymerization reactions are much faster than the step-growth polymerization, which employs a combination of different monomers [172,175,176,181]. Acrylates, methacrylates and vinyl monomers are the most widely applied building blocks during radical polymerization in 3D-printing systems. The mechanism of the reaction is also shown schematically in Figure 17.

The primary limitation to such polymer networks are observed in terms of shrinkage stresses as well as the network heterogeneity [172,182]. Furthermore, such reactions are also very sensitive to the presence of oxygen, which could react with radical species and inhibit addition reactions [137,172].

Figure 17. Schematics of radical induced chain growth polymerization of acrylates. Termination stage is represented here only with a combination step. Reproduced with permission from [183]. Copyright © 2021 Elsevier.

Monomers are the building blocks of a polymer network and greatly define the final properties of the end product. Successful completion of the polymerization reaction requires the compatibility with the 3D-printing equipment, reactivity of the monomers, appropriate absorbing characteristics of the photoinitiators and the light source. Furthermore, it is important that the printed architectures are dimensionally stable, possess the required stiffness, durability, biocompatibility and could withstand the application pressures, temperatures and other environmental conditions [53–56]. Some of the widely used commercial (meth-)acrylates are presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Structures of selected acrylates and methacrylate monomers typically used for vat photopolymerization based 3D-printing.

4.3.1.2. Cationic polymerization

Cationic polymerization is a class of chain growth polymerization, which involves the formation of cationic initiator species that activates the monomer by charge transfer. Cationic polymerization offers a range of advantages including insensitivity to oxygen, higher mechanical performance and lower shrinkage stresses in the evolved networks in comparison to radical mediated polymerization of (meth)acrylates and vinyl monomers [184,185]. On the other hand, the reaction kinetics of cationic initiated reactions is slower in comparison to widely adopted radical polymerization. The most commonly used monomers for cationic polymerization consist of epoxies and nucleophilic vinyl monomers (Figure 19) [184–186].

Figure 19. Structure of some commonly used epoxy monomers for vat photopolymerization 3D-printing.

Cationic polymerization was initially realized using cationic photoinitiators i.e. sulfonium salts and aryl iodonium, which could create reacting species as a result of illumination [164,187,188]. During epoxy ring opening reactions these highly reactive cationic initiators, attack the adjacent epoxy rings and form polyether links via cationic ring-opening polymerization (Figure 20). The chemical reactivity of the epoxies greatly depends on the structure and functionality. Generally cycloaliphatic epoxides have dual strained rings and hence, are particularly reactive towards ring opening polymerization [171]. Commercial epoxies such as (3,4-epoxycyclohexane) methyl-3,4-epoxycyclohexylcarboxylate (ECC) [189–192] and bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA) [193] are being widely used in vat photopolymerization 3D-printing [194,195].

Figure 20. Mechanism of photoacid initiated epoxy polymerization (cationic chain-growth). Produced with permission from [196], Copyright © 2000 John Wiley and Sons.

As a general requirement, the liquid resins involved in SLA based 3D-printing should have a suitable viscosity <4 Pa.s [41,134,197,198], as higher viscosity monomers hinder the exact layer thickness printing and raise the curing period. Furthermore, higher viscosity also results in a diffusion limited regime as the monomers could not effectively disperse over the building platform during consecutive building layers, hence the illuminated areas can run short of resin.

4.3.2. Step-growth polymerization

This type of polymerization reaction typically requires initiators for starting the reaction and they proceed between two or more different monomers with contrary functions in equimolar concentration. In comparison to chain-growth polymerization, the molecular weight increases slowly during the early stages of the reaction and only a single type of reaction takes place repeatedly for polymer network formation [172,175,176,181].

Polymerization takes place by the reaction of functional groups from the monomer. Initially, a dimer is formed by the combination of two monomers, and subsequently dimers react with other monomers to form trimers, which combine further to form tetramer. This process proceeds until the complete conversion is achieved [176,181]. The degree of polymerization (D_p) in step-growth reaction can be expressed using Carothers equation (Equation 7) for a given conversion (p) as [199],

$$D_p = \frac{2}{2 - pf} \quad (7)$$

While f represents the average number of functional groups for all kind of utilized monomers. Step-growth polymerization reactions are classified according to the reaction types, comprising of polyesterification, polyamidation, polycondensation or polyaddition reactions. However, they can also take place by cycloaddition reactions, electron transfer and radical coupling reactions, and atom transfer radical addition reactions [167,175,176,181]. A special category of step-growth polymerization is termed as click-reactions, which benefit from unique features such as: 1) performance at ambient conditions, 2) high yields, 3) insensitivity to water and oxygen, 4) regiospecificity and orthogonality with other reactions, 5) no side reaction or easily removable side products [200–203]. Nucleophilic ring opening reactions, copper catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC), Diels-Alder reactions, and thiol-ene/yne reactions are some well-known click reactions [200].

4.3.2.2. Thiol-ene and thiol-yne chemistry

Photopolymerization reactions based on thiol-ene or thiol-meth(acrylate) are systems which could proceed either with radical induced step-growth polymerization or thiol Michael-addition reactions (Figure 21) [171,204]. These photoreactions are also referred to as thiol-ene reactions, as the reacting group in acrylate or methacrylates is typically a $-C=C$ moiety and presents the traits of a modular click reaction [202]. During thiol-ene free radical coupling reaction, a free radical (i.e. thiyl radical) adds to the $-C=C$ groups, while thiol-Michael addition reaction (TMR), involves the catalyzed addition of thiols to an electron deficient $-C=C$ bond. In case of TMR, the reaction proceeds through anti-Markonikov route, in which a nucleophilic carbon is added to an α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group through 1,4-addition reactions [12].

Figure 21. General reaction scheme of the addition of thiols across “ene” functions: radical mediated thiol-ene versus catalyzed thiol-Michael reaction (TMR) [202].

The final product of both reactions could be the same, but the processing methodology is entirely different [202], and requires a good understanding before correctly implementing in vat photopolymerization process. Thiol-Michael reactions can be initiated with a wide range of catalysts such as Lewis acids, metals, strong basis and organometallics [205,206], and could take place even in the dark atmosphere, resulting in gelation of the liquid resins, significantly reducing their shelf-life [67]. Furthermore, the fast polymerization kinetics of TMRs also makes it very difficult to control the orthogonality. Hence onwards, we will only be discussing the radical induced thiol-ene step-growth polymerization within 3D-printing domain. From a physical point-of-view, most of the commercially available thiols are in the liquid state which makes it convenient to dissolve and quickly introduce into the photocurable resin formulations. Some commercially available alkene and thiol structures are presented in Figure 22 and 23, respectively.

Figure 22. Structure of selected alkenes and alkynes used for vat photopolymerization 3D-printing.

Figure 23. Structures of selected commercially available thiols.

The free radical reaction of thiol-ene resins involve a series of reaction stages, involving the activation of thiols via H-abstraction reaction (Figure 24), generating thiyl radicals which, could then attack the unsaturated $-C=C$ bonds and shift the active radical centers by forming the carbon centered radicals. The carbon centered radicals are able to abstract a hydrogen atom from another thiol groups and the reaction propagates by further reaction with unsaturated carbon bonds following a step-growth mechanism [202,207]. By employing acrylates or methacrylates as “ene” component, the unsaturated carbonyl bonds can also undergo homo-polymerization via addition reactions (chain-growth) giving rise to a mixed-mode reaction mechanism [207] as represented in Figure 24.

Free-radical thiol-ene reactions offer multiple advantages over conventional acrylate or methacrylate-based homo-polymerization reactions. Firstly, thiols have the ability to donate hydrogen atoms and form thiyl radicals, in the presence of peroxide radicals, hence they express insensitivity to oxygen [204,208]. Secondly, during thiol-ene reactions, flexible thioether bonds are formed, and gelation takes place at higher reaction conversions as a result of step-growth polymerization, resulting in lower shrinkage stresses and tougher polymer networks [209–211].

Figure 24. Reaction cycle representing mix-mode thiol-ene and acrylate homopolymerization. Active carbon centers can participate in chain transfer as well as chain propagation. Reproduced with permission from [202]. Copyright © 2010 John Wiley and Sons.

Moreover, thiol-ene polymers present a higher level of biocompatibility in contrast to pure acrylate/methacrylate polymerization system [212,213]. All of these advantages have made thiol-ene or thiol-(meth)acrylate reactions, one of the promising chemistries in vat photopolymerization 3D-printing, and numerous research works have adopted it in recent years [66,67,214–216].

Thiol addition reactions are not only limited to $-C=C$, but they are also proceed with $-C\equiv C$ groups from alkyne monomers [217–220]. The reaction mechanism is the same as of thiol-ene reaction but it typically involves a double addition reaction with thiyl radical, forming a vinyl sulfide intermediate additionally. Thiol-yne generates polymer networks with a higher crosslinking density and higher glass transition temperatures as compared to the thiol-ene reactions [221–223]. Some selected alkyne structures are also shown in Figure 22.

4.3.3. Hybrid (interpenetrating) polymerization

Besides photopolymerization of single network including vinyl monomers, (meth)acrylates, thiol-ene/yne or epoxies, hybrid polymerization routes yielding interpenetrating networks (IPNs) have gained increased attention over the past years. IPNs are formed by the consolidation of more than one polymerization mechanism, in a single resin formulation. Specifically designed to compensate the limitations of one type of the polymerization network, the additional polymer networks are usually exploited to improve the physico-chemical, thermal or mechanical performance of the IPN. There are many examples of photocurable interpenetrating networks and selected ones will be shortly briefed in the following section.

4.3.3.1. Dual curable networks (photo-thermal sequential cure)

Thiol-ene/yne based photopolymerized materials exhibit much better network homogeneity and reduced shrinkage stresses in comparison to pure (meth)acrylate-based polymers as discussed earlier. But the flexible core structure of the commercially available thiols, along with the formation of inherently flexible thio-ether bonds significantly limits their thermal, mechanical and physical properties [224]. This become particularly critical when 3D-printed prototypes with higher modulus, hardness and thermal resistances are required [225,226]. On the other hand, pure epoxy-based networks are brittle and possess a high temperature resistance, but suffer from poor flexibility [227].

One way to benefit from the traits of both materials is to employ a combination of these monomers. Sangermano et al. developed dual curing networks consisting of a combination of thiol, acrylate and epoxy monomers. They formulated the resins with equimolar concentration of thiol and allyl groups, and varied the concentration of epoxy monomers in the formulation. Moreover, they added 1 wt% benzophenone and 1wt% triphenylsulfonium hexafluoroantimonate as photoinitiators for thiol-acrylate and thiol-epoxy curing reactions, respectively. The formulations were UV irradiated forming a mixed-mode network composed of thiol-acrylate and epoxy segments. Due to the slow cure kinetics of the cationic ring opening reaction, a thermal post-treatment step was required to complete consume the epoxy monomers forming the second polymer network. They concluded that the addition of 50% epoxy monomer resulted in polymer networks with a T_g of 25 °C and higher modulus, in contrast to a T_g of -5 °C while using pristine thiol-acrylate chemistry [226].

Moracho et al. also studied hybrid networks consisting of epoxy monomers and thiol-ene resins. They concluded that irradiation gave the radical induced polymerization product, while an additional thermal curing was required to accelerate the epoxy ring-opening reaction. The formed interpenetrating network benefited from much better thermomechanical properties in comparison to pristine thiol-ene networks [228]. Several other

studies have also been reported on combination of radical and cationic photopolymerization to form IPNs using sequential curing [229,230].

Konuray et al. applied this concept in 3D printable resin formulations and they developed resin formulations with varying epoxy and acrylate monomers in different concentrations. The resins were photocured during SLA 3D-printing, followed by a thermal curing to achieve complete conversion of the epoxy monomers via cationic induced dark curing reactions. Using these approaches, the authors developed materials with two T_g s, corresponding to the values of the single acrylate and epoxy networks. Moreover, varying the concentrations of constituents also resulted in wide variations of T_g and thermomechanical properties [231]. Furthermore, Kuang et al. exploited a similar approach for DLP printing and used a combination of acrylate and epoxy resins for the additive manufacturing of functional devices for engineering application [232].

Griffini et al. formulated a photo-thermal curing resin using a combination of light curable acrylate and thermally curable epoxy monomers, which they applied in SLA 3D-printing. TPO-L was used as a radical photoinitiator as the SLA printer contained a light source operating at 405 nm. Instead of a cationic photoinitiator, they employed classic hardeners and accelerators for the thermal curing of the epoxy monomer in a subsequent post-baking step. They demonstrated that the T_g could be increased from 73 °C (for a pure acrylate system) to 115 °C (using a blend with a 1:1 ratio of epoxy:acrylate), along with a notable increase in the storage modulus [233].

4.3.3.2. Dual photo-curing system

In addition to the dual curing cycle (i.e. photocuring followed by thermal curing), another way to form IPNs is to exploit resin formulations, which are able to form different polymer networks through a single illumination step. This idea has been exploited by using the ability of photoinitiators to initiate both radical and cationic polymerizations [227,233,234] simultaneously under UV illumination.

Various investigations have been performed on the dual curing hybrid networks based on acrylate and epoxy as well as thiol-ene and thiol-epoxy networks. Jian et al. reported on a reaction system, which contained a combination of thiol-acrylate and thiol-epoxy resins in a single formulation. For the photopolymerization of epoxy monomers with thiols a photo-base generator was utilized and a radical photoinitiator was introduced in the precursor resin for triggering the thiol-acrylate reaction. An interpenetrating network was developed by simultaneous generation of free radicals and a strong base by UV irradiating the formulation, leading to a hybrid reaction of thiols across both epoxy and acrylate groups [235]. They further reported that the T_g of pure thiol-acrylate networks was limited to -12.3 °C, but the interpenetrating networks formed with thiol-epoxy/thiol-acrylate (75/25 wt%) could achieve a T_g of 37.6 °C. Subsequently, they tuned the resin formulations to generate hybrid polymer networks with improved storage modulus, hardness and thermal resistance.

Yu et al. developed hybrid epoxy-acrylate based resins, which they applied in SLA 3D-printing using an illumination source at 355 nm. They adopted a similar strategy of introducing both radical and cationic photoinitiators in the formulations, which could start the polymerization reactions with respective monomers upon UV irradiation, all at once. However, reaction orthogonality was not observed, instead an interpenetrating network was developed with a single network T_g [227]. They also reported that the cationic polymerization of epoxies could even take place in dark conditions limiting the storage stability of the resins.

Decker et al. developed hybrid networks, which undergo simultaneous curing of both acrylate and epoxy monomers upon UV exposure. They introduced applied cationic photoinitiators such as diaryliodonium hexafluorophosphate salts, which could not only generate protonic acid for cationic ring opening reaction of the epoxy monomers but also release free radicals in the presence of hydrogen donors. Thus, UV irradiation of such

formulations initiated both cationic and radical polymerization reactions and formed IPNs successfully [234].

Furthermore, with recent advancements in photopolymerization and increasing applications in various fields of material science, hybrid (interpenetrating) networks have evolved as an emerging area with multiple research activities being reported over the past years [76,236–240]. The application of appropriate reaction methodology along with a selection of appropriate monomers can further broaden the aspects in vat photopolymerization 3D-printing industry.

5. Progress on multi-material vat photopolymerization 3D-printing

There are primarily two strategies (Figure 25) that have been adopted by the scientific community for the development of multi-material vat photopolymerization 3D-printing technology:

1. Changing the resins during 3D-printing in a sequential manner to form a multi-material structure.
2. Printing one resin formulation but selectively activating photoreactions by changing the light source during 3D-printing.

We will briefly discuss the history of multi-material vat photopolymerization, recent works and the pros and cons of both printing approaches in the following sections.

Figure 25. Strategies for multi-material vat photopolymerization 3D-printing.

5.1. Multi-vat photopolymerization 3D-printing

The introduction of different resins using various resin vats in a vat photopolymerization 3D-printing process and fabricating the material in a chronological manner to form a multilayer structure has been well exploited by the research community. The first efforts were made by Maruo et al. in 2001 when they introduced a micro-stereolithography process, which was able to print with different photocurable resins. By using two polymer resin dosing pumps in a sequential manner, they printed two different photocurable resins in a single vat, and cured the materials by illumination with UV-light (325 nm) layer-by-layer [241].

Later on, Wicker et al. developed a multi-vat carousel assembly for multi-material stereolithography. They introduced three vats in a stereolithography setup: two of them for incorporating different photocurable resins and the third vat for the intermittent washing and drying of the printed structure [242]. Furthermore, they also demonstrated the concept of two building platforms in a multiple rotary vat setup, with a mechanical assembly to support the movement of platform and resin vat for customized multi-material

printing. However, the retrofitted apparatus was limited to a building area of 4.5 inches x 4.5 inches. Their further work on multi-vat systems was extended to 4 rotary vat assemblies in a SLA 3D-printer (Figure 26 and Figure 27), with a capability of printing resin volumes up to 9 liters [27].

Choi et al. developed a simpler and non-automated multi-material system. They realized the process by intermittently removing the vat during SLA printing, withdrawing the resin, cleaning the resin vat and introducing predetermined volumes of other resins using syringes in to the vat [28].

With these strategies, researchers were able to print multi-material 3D-structures, but the primary challenge in these concepts is the effective exchange and removal of the resin materials during the different printing steps. Furthermore, most of the multi-material vat photopolymerization works till then were adopted using top-down light-scanning methodology for 3D-printing. The platform was largely immersed into the resin volume and the 3D-printing structures were built along the z-axis. Such a printing process greatly enhances the chances of contamination and resin trapping within the confined areas of 3D-printed architecture, making it ultimately difficult to wash and perfectly clean the material during the printing steps.

Figure 26. Multi-material SLA setup developed by Choi and coworkers, reproduced with permission from [27]. Copyright © 2011 Elsevier.

Figure 27. (a) Multi-vat carousel assembly employed in SLA 3D-printing. (b) Multi-material 3D-printed articles using SLA. Reproduced with permission from [27]. Copyright © 2011 Elsevier.

In 2013, Zhou et al. proposed multi-material SLA printing via a bottom-up approach. With this set-up, the contact between the building platform and liquid resin was minimized and cleaning of only those parts of the structure was required, which are in direct contact with the resin. But their technology of multi-material 3D-printing still relied on carousel-based vat changeover. The cleaning process also involved extensive ultra-sonification and brushing, which essentially could not overcome all problems [243].

Matte et al. developed a multi-material DLP setup using an automated storage and retrieval system (ASRS). Instead of using rotary vat assemblies, they utilized a tower approach, in which different vats were provided as vertical trays. They successfully incorporated 8 resin vats in their multi-material DLP printer and significantly improved the packing density in comparison to rotary carousel storage system. Using their developed methodology, they reduced the swapping time delays observed during vats exchange in rotary systems. Furthermore, they installed a spray cleaning unit after exchange of vats to remove the entrapped resin and avoid contamination of lateral resin vats [244].

Pursuing another approach, Kowsari et al. established a multi-material DLP 3D-printing setup by installing a glass plate for delivering material puddles to achieve faster material exchange during the printing. Furthermore, they employed a novel air jet-based cleaning assembly to reduce the contamination of vats and wastage of resins, while also avoiding the damage of printed articles. Photocurable resins were placed in syringes and deposited on the glass plate layer-by-layer during printing. An air jet of 0.5 MPa, applied in 5 s intervals, was used for a cleaning of the 3D-printed structures. The printing platform was adjusted above the glass plate leaving a gap, which corresponds to the designed layer thickness. Multi-material structures were evolved using layer-by-layer introduction of the resins, intermittent cleaning and visible light curing (405 nm) [36].

Figure 28. (a) Process working schematics for multi-material SLA printing using two different monomers. (b) The chemical structure developed by monomers via multi-material SLA printing. Reproduced from [31]. Copyright © 2016 Springer.

Ge et al. reported on the multi-material printing using micro SLA technology with different acrylate monomers using two automatic exchanging vats. They utilized a mixture of mono-functional methacrylate as linear chain builder and a difunctional methacrylate as crosslinker and fabricated multifunctional structures with shape memory

properties [31]. The process employed the automatic swapping of resin chambers after printing fixed layers of each material (Figure 28).

Keneth et al. utilized combination of methacrylates having different glass transition temperatures using DLP 3D-printing to fabricate multi-material architectures. They adopted the philosophy of print, pause and exchange, steps during printing. After printing the initial design partially by using one of the resins, they stopped the DLP printer and exchanged the resin vat, filled it with the second methacrylate blend formulation and resumed the printing process for evolution of the multi-material object. Using such an approach, they exploited the materials response to thermal stimuli to create 3D objects which undergo localized shape-memory induced movements (Figure 29), without making modifications in the complete structure [40].

Figure 29. Thermally induced transitions in a double lid multi-material DLP printed box. Both lids remain close below 52 °C. At 52 °C both lids open. The inner lid closes at 58 °C. Produced from [40]. Copyright © 2020 MDPI.

Hu et al. also developed an automatic multi-vat DLP printing setup including a washing and drying chamber (Figure 30). The apparatus consisted of 3 different resin vats and they employed a moving DLP projector, which could illuminate the vat on all 3 positions, corresponding to the design. After each illumination interval, the platform was raised from the vat and transported by the motorized assembly to the washing and drying chamber, where it was washed with water and ethanol, and purged before displacing it to the next resin vat [33]. Although the technology still involved a time delay due to additional time consumption in platform transfer, cleaning and drying steps, the authors successfully 3D-printed multi-material structures.

Figure 30. (a) Conceptual diagram of multi-material DLP 3D-printing setup. (b) Overview of the actual multi-material DLP 3D-printer developed by Hu and co-workers. Reproduced with permission from [33]. Copyright © 2022 Elsevier.

As a summary of the progress in multiple vat 3D-printing, it can be concluded that the technology has evolved and advanced significantly for the additive manufacturing of 3D objects with multi-material properties in the last decade. However, there are immense limitations on account of the intermittent resin exchange mechanism where extensive cleaning is required. The process is also time consuming and even automated processes cannot ensure a complete cleaning of the printed structures during swapping between multiple vats. Moreover, the interlayers' adhesion, anisotropic properties, incompatibility of multiple polymers often results in poor material properties and pre-mature damage of the objects. Hence, an optimized multi-material 3D-printing technology using multiple vats allowing a fast building of high-performance materials still needs to be realized.

5.2. Orthogonality mediated multi-material 3D-printing

Chemo-selective multi-material printing using vat photopolymerization has evolved as a chemical strategy to spatially control the network formation traits layer-by-layer and presents the potential solution to the contamination and vat exchange problems encountered with multi-vat 3D-printing technology. The design of the resin formulations and the polymerization strategy are the key factors that determine the orthogonality control and final chemical properties of the 3D-printed articles.

Orthogonality was initially utilized in literature to describe distinct features that could not overlap [245,246], and in 1977 it was used for the first time in chemistry to represent the selective withdrawal of protecting groups in the presence of many other groups, by varying the reaction conditions [247]. Afterwards, orthogonality has been repeatedly used to illustrate the selectivity in chemical interactions [248–251].

In order to achieve concurrent and independent reactions control in a single reacting system, it is essential to induce stimuli, which could drive the selective reactions without effecting the other components in the system. Various external stimuli including heat, pH, light, redox, and electric potential have been used for reaction initiations, and among them light has been well known on account of its suitable properties including low energy consumption, spatial and temporal control and independence from other external stimuli [252,253]. On account of the light's ability to operate independent of other external stimuli, some examples of orthogonal reactions using a combination of photo and other reaction drivers already exist for complex material fabrication [254,255]. Although more important for 3D-printing vat photopolymerization are the systems based on the attributes of chromophores and their reactivity. One way to achieve the orthogonality control in multi-reaction systems is to employ different wavelengths of light (Figure 31). This chemical reaction orthogonality coupled with the application of multi-wavelength light is frequently termed as chromatic orthogonality or λ -orthogonality in chemistry [256].

Figure 31. Conceptual illustration of orthogonally evolved photopolymer networks via two different lights illumination. Polymer network 1 forms 1st layer and polymer network 2 forms 2nd layer in a subsequently building of multi-material structures.

The chemical structure of the chromophores defines the capabilities of absorbing light at certain wavelengths and initiate photochemical reactions. Hence, a rational choice of a mixture of chromophores could be utilized to independently initiate selective photochemical reactions, while numerous organic synthesis conventions and post-modifications are evolved using this reaction philosophy [257,258]. As a result, multi-wavelength light irradiation to sequentially or simultaneously initiate specific reactions, broadens the prospects of performing complicated synthesis protocols that could be challenging to drive using conventional chemical approaches. The capability to discriminately control the reaction with wavelength could give rise to materials with distinct and spatially detailed chemical and mechanical traits [22].

For the development of 3D-printed orthogonal vat photopolymerization protocols, initial attempts were made in 2019 by Schwartz et al. when they formulated a combination of acrylate and epoxy resins for DLP 3D-printing (Figure 32). Radical and cationic photoinitiators were dissolved in a single resin and illuminated with visible (long wavelength) as well as UV light (short wavelength) utilizing a so-called multi-material actinic

spatial control (MASC) strategy. Taking advantage of the reactions' orthogonality, various multi-material 3D-structures with varying spatially-induced mechanical anisotropy, swelling and network heterogeneity were fabricated by varying the illumination wavelength [259].

Figure 32. Representation of MASC strategy to achieve different networks with discrete wavelengths of light irradiation. A stiffer network was formed by cationic epoxy polymerization while a soft network was generated by radical acrylate polymerization. Reproduced from [259]. Copyright © 2019.

Figure 33 represents the conceptual illustration for achieving an orthogonal reaction control. Cationic photoinitiators (a mixture of triarylsulfonium salts) and radical photoinitiators (Irgacure 189) were utilized with their intrinsic absorption cut-off at 390 nm and 450 nm, respectively. In the first step, visible light was exploited to selectively activate the radical polymerization of acrylates by taking advantage of long wavelength absorption capability of Irgacure 819. In contrast, the short wavelength light (UV light with $\lambda = 365$ nm) was able to additionally activate triarylsulfonium salts starting the epoxy ring-opening polymerization by forming photoacids in an orthogonal manner. Multi-material objects were fabricated using a layer-by-layer approach, with one layer illuminated with visible light and the subsequent layer with UV-light. The process was repeated until the full design was 3D-printed [259]. A schematic diagram of the DLP 3D-printing process is also presented in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Customized multi-material DLP 3D-printing setup with visible and UV-projectors. Scanning process control was carried out using an integrated laptop. Reproduced from [259]. Copyright © 2019 Springer.

Rossegger et al. also developed a vat photopolymerization 3D-printing setup using DLP technology in which they introduced a spatially activated photo-acid in an orthogonal manner. The resin formulation comprised thiol and acrylate monomers along with a

visible light photoinitiator. In addition, triphenylsulfonium phosphate was added as a latent transesterification catalyst (photo-acid), with the capability to release the Brønsted acid under UV-irradiation. The resin formulation was DLP 3D-printed with visible-light (405 nm) as well as UV-light (365 nm) projectors as presented in Figure 34. Cured structures were evolved by illuminating the resin layer-by-layer with visible-light and UV-light in an alternating manner. In this way the photoacid was activated orthogonally in desired layers, which was exploited as catalyst to initiate dynamic exchange reactions at elevated temperature [216].

Figure 34. (a) Constituents of the resin formulation for selectively activating a transesterification catalyst in thiol-acrylate photopolymers, (b) dual light wavelength DLP 3D-printer setup, (c) visible light mediated network formation during DLP 3D-printing, (d) UV light triggered activation of Brønsted acids acting as a transesterification catalyst. Figures redrawn from [216].

5.3. Grayscale photopolymerization 3D-printing

Grayscale illumination is a process for locally controlling the light doses during 3D-printing, leading to a spatially customized crosslink density in the polymer network. The technology employs a single vat photopolymerization unit, but could also be based on multiple vat units.

The core methodology is based on grayscale processing, in which images are scanned in a monochromic light setting to induce location specific properties within the network. The designed articles are sliced to images corresponding to each illuminating layer and materials are built in a layer-by-layer approach. Mathematical software tools are then utilized to process the individual images and setup the grayscale distribution according to the preferred material properties. Grayscale images are derived from the normalization of red-green-blue (RGB) values to determine grayscale percentages, and classified from 100% (dark scale) to 0% (full intensity). These programmed images with grayscale impressions are transmitted to the light projection modules for illumination and vat photopolymerization. Higher grayscale levels result in a lower crosslink density and hence, lower modulus of the materials. Empirical relationships are further derived by determining the conversion of reactive functional groups with light illumination [260].

Kuang et al. formed functionally graded materials having a wide range of mechanical properties using grayscale vat photopolymerization. Their technology of grayscale printing was based on digital light processing. As photocurable resins, a combination of mono-functional and di-functional acrylates along with a methacrylate bearing epoxy moieties, amine crosslinkers and photoinitiator were selected. Initially, acrylates in the resin formulation were allowed to radically photopolymerize leading to a polymer network formation, which could fix the designed structure [260]. Underexposed regions during grayscale polymerization resulted in unreacted monomers, which could result into poor mechanical properties [261–264]. A second thermal curing step was introduced to convert the unreacted monomer and improve the mechanical properties of the underexposed grayscale regions. The primary contribution to thermal curing was observed from crosslinking reaction of diamine with acrylate and epoxide monomers [260]. The thermal curing of the articles was carried out at below 120°C, which effectively avoided the self-initiation of the acrylate homopolymerization [265]. Materials formed with higher grayscale (93%) factors

were typically soft and had a Young's modulus up to 1.4 MPa, while stiffer material regions were formed by adjusting the grayscale to 0% having a Young's modulus up to 1.2 GPa. With this approach, a wide range of graded materials were fabricated with a T_g varying between 14 to 68°C [260].

Wu et al. further devised the grayscale light patterns to control the light intensity of light projections. DLP vat photopolymerization technology was adopted to develop spatially varied materials by illuminating each layer for the same time, and employing the digital mask patterns, which ultimately varied the crosslinking density distribution. The fundamental principle was based on the fact that dark scaling corresponds to lower light intensity and thus, gave rise to materials with lower crosslinking density. Mathematical integration software such as Matlab and Solidworks were employed to obtain grayscale values of each pixel of the slicing image. Grayscale values ranged between 0 – 255, from a completely black to a completely white scale respectively. These grayscales were fed into the digital micromirror device projector, which transmitted the grayscale patterns in to the corresponding light intensities, in a way that completely black patterns (0 grayscale) led to 0% light illumination and completely white patterns (255 grayscale) led to 100% light intensity. Hence, the crosslinking degree was spatially controlled by transforming grayscale patterns into light intensity distribution in each layer while using resin formulations containing conventional acrylates and methacrylates [266].

Muralidharan et al. employed a combination of thiol-acrylate and thiol-ene based hydrogels for developing composite materials by employing grayscale SLA technology. For pursuing the grayscale illumination strategy, the resin formulations were experimentally studied to draw relationships between the illumination intensity, illumination time and reaction conversions. The reaction conversions corresponded with the crosslink density, which was also verified with swelling test measurements. In this way, regions of soft and stiff materials were successfully integrated in a composite structure by employing grayscale impressions [267].

6. Applications of multi-material vat photopolymerization 3D-printing

Vat polymerization 3D-printing technologies have clearly presented themselves as an outstanding competitor among all the additive manufacturing technologies on account of their high printing resolution, building speed and surface finish of final products. The ease of upscaling and simplicity of combining various chemistries has given rise to complex 3D-designs, which could be quickly realized as real objects at lower costs. In this section, we discuss the applications of vat photopolymerization based multi-material 3D-printing in various material related fields.

6.1. Bio-mimicking by combining soft and hard segments

The existence of natural high-performance biological structures and evolution over the past hundreds of years has been a great motivation for the design and fabrication of materials that could mimic the natural bodies [271]. The complex structural geometry of bio-inspired architectures has surpassed the complexity limits that were achievable using additive manufacturing with single materials. Mimicking the architectures of natural bodies such as bones and nacre, which comprise of two different materials as a brick and mortar design (stiff and soft part respectively), for achieving higher strength and energy-dissipation characteristics, is nearly impossible to fabricate by using single-material 3D-printing technologies [278]. Multi-material 3D-printing could revolutionize the material developments for replicating such multi-functional, multiscale natural entities [272, 273].

Schwartz et al. worked on multi-material vat photopolymerization and printed polymer structures, which mimic an anisotropic human hand. They used a stiff polymer for forming the internal bone structure and a soft polymer, wrapping the rigid structure, by applying dual-wavelength photopolymerization. A combination of acrylate and epoxy resin was formulated and orthogonally cured with visible light yielding a soft acrylate

network, whilst the stiff epoxy-acrylate IPN was formed using cationic polymerization (UV illumination) [259]. Anisotropic compression in multi-material architectures was attained through well-defined soft and hard segments. Figure 35 represents the multi-material DLP 3D-printed hand structure.

Figure 35. (a) Arbitrary scale DLP projection images, upper design (bones) printed with UV-light, lower design printed with visible-light. (b) Multi-material DLP 3D-printed hand using UV and visible light projections. Scale bar represents 25 mm. Reproduced from [259]. Copyright © 2019 Springer.

These anisotropic properties could also be tuned to develop a different set of multi-material structures by varying the contents of acrylate and epoxy in the formulation. Furthermore, the capability of such multi-material systems to spatially control the strength and anisotropic features by controlling the content and location of soft and rigid polymers is a technically relevant aspect in bioinspired materials.

Furthermore, metamaterials with negative Poisson's ratio could be also developed using multi-material vat photopolymerization. Such materials hold the capability of becoming thicker perpendicular to the applied force in stretched conditions. This property could be particularly useful in prevention of fracture and impact resonance. Chen et al. fabricated metamaterial lattices consisting of spatially distributed rigidity over the material by employing an automatic resin switching process. They employed resins comprising of a stiff, low molecular mass polyfunctional tri-acrylate and very flexible, high molecular mass oligomeric polyether(meth)acrylate to visualize hard and soft segments. By varying the content of these monomers, they could also tune the modulus and Poisson's ratio in microlattices over a broad range (Figure 36) [268].

Figure 36. (a) Components of resin formulation, (b) tunable stiffness bandwidth in photocured polymers by varying concentration of A and B components and (c) physical representation of printed architectures with varying compositions. Reproduced from [268]. Copyright © 2018 Springer.

Peterson et al. developed materials by spatially controlling the crosslinking density with greyscale DLP technology. Multi-material lattices and trusses were fabricated with distinctive mechanical features by 3D-printing using commercially available acrylate-based resins. Octet trusses with lower crosslinking density at the joints and higher crosslinking density at the beams were produced, which significantly improved the mechanical properties of trusses in comparison to constant greyscale printing [261]. Kuang et al. developed compression lattices and also took use of greyscale DLP 3D-printing for tuning the deformations, negative Poisson's ratio and structural anisotropy in their work [260].

6.2. Bio-medical applications

Multimaterial vat photopolymerization 3D-printing has been a very prominent technology for mimicking the biological structures and synthetic tissue architectures. Owing to the ability of multi-materials to incorporate different properties into a single complex, numerous cell types and natural tissues could be developed in a reasonable time scale. Until now, numerous complex scaffolds with different layers of cells [35, 93], layers of tunable stiffness [125], spots functionalized with cells [17, 33], degrading polymer channels for controlled cell placement [107, 108], have been developed and fabricated by using multi-material 3D-printing.

Wu et al. developed a customized vat interchanging SLA system for the fabrication of a bi-phase osteochondral scaffold for implantation in a goat's knee joint. The scaffold was developed using poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA) acting as the cartilage scaffold in the multi-material and a ceramic beta-tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) serving as the bone tissue scaffold [269]. Furthermore, tissue models have also been developed using multi-material vat photopolymerization technology. PEG and hyaluronic acid derivatives were implemented as degradable scaffolds in a cell-laden biopolymer to give rise to channels in vascular model and liver tissues [270,271]. The process also exploited DLP 3D-printing with the exchanging materials in the resin vat (Figure 37).

Figure 37. Cell brick 3D-printing process of liver (a) virtual 3D-design, (b) microscopic image of the printed multi-material hydrogel cell-laden, (c) multi-material DLP 3D-printing setup used for liver design printing. Reproduced from [270]. Copyright © 2018 MDPI.

Moreover, maskless microfluidics-enabled multi-material 3D-printers using DLP technology were used to fabricate various models of tissues geometry, such as muscle strips, angiogenesis and muscular skeleton joints by employing polymer precursor resins including poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA) and gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA) in different compositions (Figure 38) [272].

Figure 38. (a) Tumor angiogenesis model: (i) Illustration of tumor angiogenesis model; (ii) schematic of the mask for 3D-printing; (iii) bioprinted MCF7 cell (blue)-laden microvascular bed of GelMA, (iv) bioprinted cell (blue)-laden microvascular bed of GelMA seeded with cells (green) in the channels. (b) Skeletal muscle model: (i) schematic showing the skeletal muscle tissue; (ii) schematic of the mask for 3D-printing; (iii) bioprinted structure of GelMA containing patterned cells (red) and fibroblasts (blue); (iv) Presto blue measurements of cell proliferation in the printed structures. (c) A tendon-to-bone insertion model: (i) schematic of the tendon-to-bone insertion site; (ii) schematic of the mask for printing; (iii) bright-field optical image showing a bioprinted dye-laden GelMA structure; (iv) bioprinted structure of GelMA containing patterned osteoblasts (blue), MSCs (red), and fibroblasts (green). Produced with permission from [272]. Copyright © 2018 MDPI.

Moreover, many other studies describe the use of stereolithography with exchanging resin systems for additive manufacturing of biocompatible multi-material polymers such as polyethylene glycol dimethacrylate and polyethylene glycol diacrylate [35,273–286].

Figure 39. Visual presentation of a (multilayer) polypill under a) optical microscope b) Raman mapping. Each layer presents a different drug printed layer. Work picked up from [273]. Copyright © 2019 MDPI.

Multi-material 3D-printed polypills have also been developed in recent years using SLA technology, with exchange vats during fabrication. Drugs are introduced into biocompatible photocurable resins in required doses and illuminated for curing and structuring [273,274]. This could support patients to undertake defined volumes of medicine, multiple medicines in a single shot as well as reduce the non-adherence. Figure 39 represents a multi-material polypill developed using a blend of 6 medical drugs (naproxen, aspirin, paracetamol, caffeine, chloramphenicol, and prednisolone) in PEGDA and

printed layer-by-layer using each blend formulation [273]. Furthermore, some other applications of multi-material vat photopolymerization in bio-medical industry are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Applications of multimaterial vat photopolymerization in various bio-medical areas

Applications	Printing materials	Methodology	Reference
Scaffolds for tissue engineering	PEGDA, PEGDMA	Resin exchange, SLA	[275]
Multilayer layer polypills	PEGDA + dissolved drug	Resin exchange, SLA	[273]
Multilayer polypills	PEGDA, PEGDMA + dissolved drug	Resin exchange, SLA	[274]
Tissue porous scaffolds	PEGDA, Commercial photocurable resins, + Leachable salt particulates	DLP	[276]
Bioactive scaffolds	PEGDA, PEGDMA, + fluorescently labeled components	Resin exchange, SLA	[277]
Neovasculature	PEGDA, PEGDMA, + Murine cells	Resin exchange, SLA	[278]
Constructs with Encapsulated Cells	PEGDA + human dermal fibroblasts	Resin exchange, SLA	[279]
Piezoelectric acoustic sensor	PEGDA + barium titanate nanopowder + multi-walled carbon nanotubes	Resin exchange, DLP	[280]
Cell encapsulation	PEGDA + cells	Resin exchange, SLA	[281]
Multi-material cantilevers	poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA) and acrylic-PEG-collagen (PC)	Resin exchange, SLA	[282]
Selective Porous Barriers	PEGDA: MW 258, MW 575, MW 700	Resin exchange, SLA	[35]
Biological sensors	PEGDA, commercial resin, + biomolecules	Resin exchange, SLA	[283]
Tissue scaffolds	PEGDA+ fluorescently-labeled polystyrene microparticles	Resin exchange, SLA	[284]
Spatially designed biological sensor	oxidized methacrylic alginate, poly(ethylene glycol) methyl ether methacrylate, PEGDA + cells	Resin exchange, SLA	[285]
Cells interactive sensors	Gelatin methacrylate, PEGDA, fluorescent dextrans, cells	Resin exchange, SLA	[286]

6.3. Stimuli response behavior and robotic-actuators

Stimuli responsive behavior represents the nature of materials to exhibit physico-chemical transitions as a result of changes in their environment [287]. Multi-material 3D-printed polymers could offer exceptional traits of stimuli responsiveness due to their inherent structural features. The presence of two or more polymer networks in a composite material could generate different responses based on the driving force and numerous works are reported in this direction.

Kuang et al. adapted greyscale DLP 3D-printing to create multi-material polymer networks with a T_g ranging from 14 – 68 °C within a single multi-material structure, by spatially varying the illumination intensity. The authors took use of the broad temperature range and developed shape memory strategies by actuating the 3D-printed parts at different temperatures [260]. Furthermore, Wu et al. developed structures based on PEGDA, butyl acrylate and butyl methacrylate comprising of regions with varying cross-linking density. These domains reacted to solvent absorption and swelling in varying extent, resulting in spatially controlled shrinkage and reversible bending deformations [288].

Keneth et al. exploited DLP 3D-printing to prepare multi-material structures with tailored T_g , which were used to induce motions with thermal or photo-stimuli. Polycaprolactone methacrylate (PCLMA), and a mixture of *N*-vinylcaprolactam and PCLMA were introduced as two different polymer precursors in two different resin formulation. Multi-material boxes were fabricated by initially printing the structures with the first formulation, pausing the printer and adding the second resin in the vat for printing with a resin mixture. The shape memory-based activations were carried out by placing the 3D-printed box in a hot water bath (Figure 40). Pure PCLMA was activated at 52 °C, which resulted in opening of the box-top lid, while mixed resin was activated at 58 °C resulting in closure of the inset box-lid [40].

Figure 40. (Top) 3D-printed box with two lids. The box opens at 52 °C and closes at 58 °C. (Bottom) Results of the finite element simulation. Red and blue colors in the first figure on the left denote pure and mixed ink, respectively. Reproduced from [40]. Copyright © 2020 MDPI.

Ge et al. also developed multi-materials with spatially controlled shape memory properties. They synthesized methacrylate-based copolymers and varied the reaction constituents and compositions, obtaining photopolymer networks with T_g values varying between 50 and 180 °C. In addition, the modulus could be adjusted between 1 MPa and 100 MPa. SLA 3D-printing of multi-material structures was carried out by an automatic

swapping of the resin vats according to the sliced 3D-design [31]. Various designs of grippers were 3D-printed and programming of the transitions over a wide temperature range by controlling resin properties was presented (Figure 41).

Figure 41. 3D-printed multi-material grippers: (a) different sizes and designs of grippers 3D-printed, b) illustration of transitions between printed and temporary shapes as a function of temperature, c) gripper used to lift a bolt assembly. Reproduced with permission from [31]. Copyright © 2016 Springer.

Furthermore, they developed a multi-material flower structure with inner petals having a T_g of 56 °C, and the outer petals having a T_g of 43 °C. All petals were manually closed at 70 °C and then cooled down to 20 °C, to fix the structure (programming step). Figure 42(a), presents the structure of petals after cooling stage. The temperature was then increased up to 50 °C, to allow the outer petals to expand, resulting into blooming (Figure 42 (b)), while the internal petal still remained closed. Once the temperature was increased up to 70 °C, the inner petals also opened up to recover the original shape of the flower [31].

Figure 42. Stimuli responsive behavior of a multi-material 3D-printed flower: (a) Programmed (temporary) shape of the multi-material flower held at 20 °C, (b) heating up to 50 °C resulting in flower’s outer buds opening, (c) the flower fully bloomed at 70 °C, (d)–(f) simulation images of the complete multi-material flower blooming process. Reproduced with permission from [31]. Copyright © 2016 Springer.

Thrasher et al. designed multi-material pneumatic grippers, Gyroid lattice, Octet truss and fabricated them by applying multi-material vat photopolymerization. During the printing process they employed several photocurable resins named as low modulus flexible, high modulus flexible and hard material in a DLP 3D-printing setup. The designed number of layers was printed and then the printing was paused followed by replacement of the photocurable resin in the vat [289]. Using this approach, a multi-material gripper was developed as presented in Figure 43.

Figure 43. (A) Multimaterial 3D-printed pneumatic gripper, descending, pneumatically actuating, and grabbing a plastic ball. (B) Schematic illustration of the multi-material gripper before (left) and after (right) pneumatic actuation. Ball diameter = 38 mm. Reproduced from [289]. Copyright © 2017 ACS Publications.

Rossegger et al. took advantage of two transition temperatures in the developed multi-material structures using the dual wavelength vat photopolymerization approach.

Whilst the thiol-acrylate network was formed at 405, UV irradiation at 365 nm locally activated a transesterification catalyst, which resulted in dynamic exchange reactions at elevated temperature. Above the vitrification temperature (T_v) the UV irradiated domains become malleable, which is exploited to locally change the shape memory properties. Figure 44 (a) presents a bar, in which one half was printed with visible light and the other one printed with UV light and hence, contained the activated Brønsted acid [216].

During the programming step, the temperature of the gripper (permanent shape) was increased above T_v in a U-shaped mold, which turned the material from both ends, while the shape of the bar was fixed by cooling down to 10°C (Figure 44b, shape II). Further heating of the material above T_g resulted into a special shape with the UV activated side still bended, while the visible light activated side regressed back to the permanent bar shape (Figure 44b, shape III).

Similar experiment was repeated with a gripper (Figure 44c), in which two arms were printed with visible light and the other two with UV light (Figure 44a). After the programming step only the localized motion of the visible light exposed arms was observed, while the UV activated arms remained locked in programmed positions on account of the Brønsted acid catalyzed topological rearrangements (Figure 44c, shape III) [216].

Figure 44. (a) Illustrations of the printing set-up of the rectangular bar and the grippers, (b) the permanent, programming and spatially controlled shaping experiment and (c) permanent, programming and spatially controlled state of multimaterial gripper under thermal stimuli. Figures redrawn from [216].

Furthermore, several other applications of stimuli-responsive materials formed by multi-material vat photopolymerization have been reported in the recent years and summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Stimuli-responsive materials printed by multi-material vat photopolymerization

Applications	Stimuli	Printing materials	Multimaterial strategy	Reference
Hydrogel cantilevers and actuators	Chemical stimuli	Poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA) and acrylic-PEG-collagen (PC) mixtures	Resin exchange in vat, SLA	[282]
Hydrogels	Thermal stimuli	Poly(<i>N</i> -isopropylacrylamide), <i>N,N'</i> -Methylene-bis(acrylamide) mixtures	Resin exchange in vat, SLA	[290]
Hinges, robotic arms, bars and sheets	Thermal stimuli	Bisphenol A ethoxylate diacrylate (BPADA), glycidyl methacrylate (GMA), <i>n</i> -butyl acrylate (BA), a diamine cross-linker [poly(propylene glycol)]	Grayscale DLP 3D-printing	[260]

Hydrogels	Osmotic pressure, temperature and pH	bis(2-aminopropyl ether); D230], mixtures	2- <i>N,N'</i> -	1. Swelling rates via high surface area patterning, 2. Crosslinking density via photo-exposure, 3. chemical composition via resin vat exchange	[291]
		<i>N</i> -Isopropylacrylamide, carboxyethylacrylate, ethylenebisacrylamide			

6.4. Multi-material structures with self-healing function

Vitrimers are a class of materials with intrinsic dynamic bonds within the chemically crosslinked networks [292]. These dynamic bond exchanges are thermally activated and result in a microscopic reflow of the material under the application of certain force, while maintaining the structural integrity of the cured architectures. Vitrimers have been known for their ability to self-heal and recycle under the application of heat and mechanical stimuli [66,67,293,294].

Pure acrylate and thiol-acrylate based 3D-printed vitrimers using vat photopolymerization have been developed in recent years, comprising of transesterification based dynamic reactions [66,67,183,215,293]. Rossegger et al. developed vitrimeric systems using dual wavelength vat photopolymerization technology. By orthogonal activation of Brønsted acid catalysts in UV-exposed regions, transesterification reactions could be locally activated within the 3D-printed structures, which were further exploited for thermo-activated healing. The quantification of dynamic response is carried out in terms of stress-relaxation experiments, during which the time decay of the constantly applied stress is measured. Figure 45a, represents the dynamic responses obtained by incorporation of photoacid generator in multimaterials formed using vat photopolymerization 3D-printing process [216].

Figure 46. (a) Normalized stress relaxation behavior of multimaterials over time at various temperatures. (b) Arrhenius plot of UV activated multimaterials derived from measured relaxation times. Data replotted from [216].

All UV-activated multimaterial samples represented reasonable stress relaxation properties, but the non-UV activated multimaterials and the samples without photoacid generators exhibited very slow stress relaxation behavior, which confirmed the exceptional activity of dynamic reactions in UV-irradiated domains. Furthermore, the relaxation time behavior over various temperatures follows a linear trend (Figure 45b), which is

also a characteristic feature of vitrimeric materials [295,296], and hence confirms the great prospects of orthogonally fabricated multi-materials in the field of vitrimers.

7. Outlook and prospective

Additive manufacturing of materials has presented a great potential in the last decade, and has been adopted under many technology subdivisions by material researchers and the industrial community. The desire of mankind to mimic nature and to create materials that could offer multifunctional traits like human bones, soft matter with supporting structure and natural bodies, has given rise to multi-materials and many new additive manufacturing technologies. Vat photopolymerization has become a popular technology among 3D-printing technologies due to the excellent printing resolution, dimensional stability, high quality surface finish and fast processing, but the technology seriously suffer from the limited functionalities of resins and materials for vat photopolymerization that could be processed and photo-cured [50]. Customized resins are synthesized at research scales to achieve the required traits but the process becomes time and energy intensive, along with a higher cost of the encountered raw materials and synthesis assemblies.

Hence, on one side it is important to discover new resin material chemistries while on the other hand a focus should be put on utilizing the available ones in an effective way and make the most out of them. One way to achieve this is the multi-material approach to take the advantage of what is in hand or commercially available.

Multi-material 3D-photopolymerization could offer the advantages of combined material chemistries along with the cumulative advantages of vat-polymerization, but suitable strategies need to be built, for developing the process. The capability to freely integrate multiple materials having diverse mechanical, biological, optical and electrical properties could turn in to the biggest aspect of the current decade for making 3D-printing further competitive.

However, the actual level of multi-material vat photopolymerization based materials are simplistic and mostly based on multi vat processes. Such systems result in broadly contaminated products and suffer from extensive cleaning and time delays during inter vat changeover. In contrast, the chemical advancements in orthogonality mediated multi-materials are limited and needs further developments to advance the complexity and integration levels of materials industry. Application of two wavelengths for curing monomers is an attractive feature for network functionalization in photo-chemistry.

The selective and orthogonal photoreactions in the presence of two or more photochromes could give rise to spatially and temporally controlled multimaterials with superior levels of integrity and interlayer interactions. Multi-wavelength light sources, which could spatially activate the distributed chromophores could form different networks with distinctive photo-illumination.

The combination of epoxy and acrylate monomers, and taking advantage of the photo-selective polymerization i.e. cationic and radical polymerization using dual-wavelength vat photopolymerization has already been used to fabricate multi-material networks at different wavelengths. As a future prospect, we believe that the combination of photoreactive monomers such (meth)acrylates, epoxies, vinyl monomer or alkynes with the cycloaddition reaction such as photo-favored $[2\pi+2\pi]$ and $[4\pi+4\pi]$ mechanisms could develop multimaterials with orthogonality mediated network formations.

Photocuring of polymeric resins in photoresists has been one of the earliest technologies that has been developed for micro-structures and surface treatments [297,298]. Whilst vat photopolymerization technologies have been reported in late 20th century they employ similar principles that originate from photoresists. Photoresists formation also relies on analogous chemical ingredients as of today vat photopolymerization technology with the difference of transmission from smaller to macro-level features development. Latest trends and technological advancements have diverted interests from simplistic photoresists and vat photopolymerization technologies to dual-wavelength photocuring systems, as they offer the possibility to locally form different polymer networks

[251,299,300] disparately and various studies have been presented in recent years in this direction [301,302].

Photocycloaddition reactions offer the capability to locally switch material characteristics reversibly by wavelength selective network formation and cleavage reactions. Photo-dimers could form at typical long wavelength > 300 nm (low energy), while cycle-reversion could occur when exposed with short wavelengths light of < 300 nm (high energy). $[2\pi + 2\pi]$ cycloaddition reactions represent a class of photoreactions employing styrylpyrenes, coumarins and thymins and possess attractive traits of selective bonding and debonding under wavelength selective illumination. These monomers find special applications in photo induced self-healing, photo-triggered shape memory and reversible photoresists.

Coumarin represents another photochrome which finds applications in micro and macromolecular applications [303–306]. Such monomers undergo $[2\pi+2\pi]$ cycloaddition reactions with UV illumination (350 nm) forming cyclobutene rings (Figure 46) [306], whilst irradiation with low wavelength light (254 nm) could photocleave the crosslinks in a reversible manner [303,307].

Figure 46. Coumarin side groups undergoing $[2\pi+2\pi]$ cycloaddition reaction upon UV irradiation. Reproduced with permission from [308]. Copyright © 2018 Elsevier.

Anthracene monomers are also well known in photochemistry on account of their ability to undergo $[4\pi + 4\pi]$ cycloaddition reactions under photo-illumination in the range of UV-visible light, forming dimers [309–313]. These monomers possess fluorescence properties, which make them distinct from the dimerized state where the fluorescence is fully lost. Barner-Kowollik et al. took advantage of photocuring properties of acrylates bearing anthracene moieties and presented a multi-materials formation strategy using direct laser writing (DLW). By DLW, they formed network using radical polymerization of acrylates, which also served the purpose of cleaving partially existing anthracene dimers. Whilst further illumination with LED light of 415 nm resulted in cycloaddition reaction of anthracene forming dimers via $[4\pi+4\pi]$ cycloaddition reactions. The higher laser illumination times during DLW resulted into higher fluorescence generation as a result of anthracene dimers cleavage reactions [314].

A promising chemistry relying on chromophores in wavelength mediated photo-activation is the *o*-nitrobenzyl ether family, which have the ability to undergo a cleavage reaction in UV_A region and are transparent to visible light spectrum [315]. Such chromophores find applications in photo-resists [316] and local drug release [317,318]. Photolabile *o*-nitrobenzyl esters have been implemented in thiol-click photo reactions for wavelength-based modifications of surface properties, reactivity and thermomechanical properties [319,320]. Radl and co-workers prepared switchable photoresists by introducing *o*-nitrobenzyl ester moieties in visible light curable thiol-ene networks. Whilst the network was formed by exposure at 405 nm, the covalent link could be selectively cleaved in a subsequent UV exposure step [321]. Barner-Kowollik et al. synthesized an acrylate-based monomer with *o*-nitrobenzyl ether chromophore groups (Figure 47), and radically photopolymerized them under 900 nm wavelength light illumination. Furthermore, employing the photocleavage capabilities of *o*-nitrobenzyl ether groups, they spatially erased the microstructures at 700 nm [316].

Figure 47. Representational diagram of printing and cleaving process. (a) Structure of the acrylate with pendant *o*-nitrobenzyl ester (ONB) monomer. (b) Micro-fabrication using DLW (900 nm wavelength) via radical photo-polymerization of acrylates. (c) Selective cleavage of the resist at 700 nm wavelength through *o*-NB cleavage. (d) UV-vis spectrum of the ONB monomers. Arrows indicate the corresponding two-photon wavelengths for printing and cleaving. Reproduced with permission from [316]. Copyright © 2019 John Wiley and Sons.

Romano and co-workers also applied direct laser writing techniques to inscribe micropatterns within thiol-ene photopolymers containing photolabile *o*-nitrobenzyl ester links but without the requirement of a development step in solvents [322]. The local change in the surface properties was further exploited to covalently attach bio-molecules.

Bialas et al. developed macromolecular dual-photoresists based on orthogonal reaction approach [297], by adding a photocaged diene generated from *o*-methyl benzaldehyde groups (oMBA), capable of undergoing dimerization under UV activation [323], and styrylpyrene units forming $[2\pi+2\pi]$ dimers under visible light activation [324]. oMBA didn't react under visible light illumination, while styrylpyrene dimerization was effectively avoided at UV illumination spectrum, with maximum levels of photocaged oMBA reactivity (Figure 48) [297].

Figure 48. Purple area: *o*-MBA (λ_1 maximum = 330 nm purple) and turquoise area: StyP (λ_2 maximum = 435 nm) – activations for implementing a λ -orthogonal photoresist. Reproduced with permission from [297]. Copyright © 2019 John Wiley and Sons.

O-methyl benzaldehydes, *N*-ethyl-maleimides and styrylpyrene groups have also shown orthogonal reaction approaches, with thermo-activated $[4\pi+2\pi]$ Diels-Alder chemistry [297].

Alves et al. utilized di-thioacetal-protected aldehyde groups in combination with oMBA to orthogonally induce deprotection of monomers along with the activation of oMBA using visible light and UV light in a sequential manner. After activation, oMBA formed *o*-quinodimethane, which could further undergo thermally induced $[4\pi+2\pi]$ cycloaddition reaction with suitable electron deficient dienophiles such as *N*-ethylmaleimide [325].

To summarize these aspects, the potential is great for combining state of the art resins with photo-driven cycloaddition reactions. Such processes could proceed with excellent orthogonal chemistry and could offer various functional properties within a multi-material structure. Furthermore, broadening of the chemical's library having a range of mechanical and thermal properties could revolutionize the application areas and hence, a great market potential could be predicted for multi-materials.

From a hardware point of view, to date, limited progress has been reported with dual wavelength 3D-printing. The number of commercially available printers offering dual illumination projections are scarce and the ones available also suffer from lower printing capacities. A strong need of the hour is to promote the manufacturing of 3D-printers with greater manufacturing capacities (larger resin vats) along with the capabilities to modify the wavelength of light over a broad range. This could further expand the applicability of photoinitiators and monomers in multi-material 3D-printing systems.

8. Conclusions

In summary, the progress in vat photopolymerization 3D-printing and especially multi-material fabrication has made significant advancements in the global efforts for developing materials, which mimic nature. The applications of multi-material concepts in biological systems, stimuli responsive actuators, self-healing and functionally advanced materials in industry has been a center of attention in the recent decade. However, as an emerging manufacturing process, there are certain challenges and bottle necks in terms of material chemistries, printing capacities, hardware shortfall, design strategies, purity and quality of the fabricated structures. With a detailed discussion on additive manufacturing, competitive technologies, vat photopolymerization, multi-material progress, underlying mechanisms and material chemistries, we are optimistic that this review provides the readers with the key information for selection and implementation of effective multi-material strategies in general, and particularly in the field of photopolymerization. Vat photopolymerization multi-material printing is one of the best technologies of the time to form complex architectures with excellent resolution in a cost-effective manner. To enhance the functionality, endurance and integration of materials, the conjunction and streamlining of the smart designs, material chemistries, building software and equipment is necessary, which could ultimately stimulate the development of multi-materials and could revolutionize the human community in coming future.

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